

Top 20 Cited Article in Computer Science & Information Technology

**International Journal of Computer Science and
Information Technology (IJCSIT)**

Google Scholar Citation

Cited by [VIEW ALL](#)

	All	Since 2016
Citations	8388	5605
h-index	46	33
i10-index	212	160

ISSN: 0975-3826(online); 0975-4660 (Print)

<http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit.html>

EDGE DETECTION TECHNIQUES FOR IMAGE SEGMENTATION

Muthukrishnan.R¹ and M.Radha²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Statistics, Bharathiar University, Coimbatore.

² Research Scholar, Department of Statistics, Bharathiar University, Coimbatore.

ABSTRACT

Interpretation of image contents is one of the objectives in computer vision specifically in image processing. In this era it has received much awareness of researchers. In image interpretation the partition of the image into object and background is a severe step. Segmentation separates an image into its component regions or objects. Image segmentation t needs to segment the object from the background to read the image properly and identify the content of the image carefully. In this context, edge detection is a fundamental tool for image segmentation. In this paper an attempt is made to study the performance of most commonly used edge detection techniques for image segmentation and also the comparison of these techniques is carried out with an experiment by using MATLAB software.

KEYWORDS

Computer Vision , Image Segmentation , Edge detection, MATLAB.

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/jcsit/1211csit20.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/iicsit2011_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] Canny, J. F (1983) Finding edges and lines in images, Master's thesis, MIT. AI Lab. TR-720.
- [2] Canny, J. F (1986) "[A computational approach to edge detection](#)", IEEE Transaction on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, 8, 679-714.
- [3] Courtney. P & N. A. Thacker (2001) "[Performance Characterization in Computer Vision: The Role of Statistics in Testing and Design](#)", Chapter in: "Imaging and Vision Systems: Theory, Assessment and Applications", Jacques Blanc-Talon and Dan Popescu (Eds.), NOVA Science Books.
- [4] Hanzi Wang (2004) Robust Statistics for Computer Vision: Model Fitting, Image Segmentation and Visual Motion Analysis, Ph.D thesis, Monash University, Australia.
- [5] Huber, P.J. (1981) Robust Statistics, Wiley New York.
- [6] Kirsch, R. (1971) "[Computer determination of the constituent structure of biological images](#)", Computers and Biomedical Research, 4, 315–328.
- [7] Lakshmi,S & V.Sankaranarayanan (2010) "[A Study of edge detection techniques forsegmentation computing approaches](#)", Computer Aided Soft Computing Techniques for Imaging and Biomedical Applications, 35-41.
- [8] Lee, K.. M, Meer, P. & et al. (1998) "[Robust Adaptive Segmentation of Range Images](#)", IEEE Trans. Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, 20(2), 200-205.
- [9] Marr, D & E. Hildreth (1980) "[Theory of edge detection](#)", Proc. Royal Society of London, B, 207, 187–217.
- [10] Marr, D(1982) Vision, Freeman Publishers.
- [11] Marr, P & Doron Mintz, D. & et al. (1991) "[Robust Regression for Computer Vision: A Review](#)", International Journal of Computer Vision, 6(1), 59-70.
- [12] Orlando, J, Tobias & Rui Seara (2002) "[Image Segmentation by Histogram Thresholding Using Fuzzy Sets](#)", IEEE Transactions on Image Processing, Vol.11, No.12, 1457-1465.
- [13] Punam Thakare (2011) "[A Study of Image Segmentation and Edge Detection Techniques](#)", International Journal on Computer Science and Engineering, Vol 3, No.2, 899-904.

- [14] Rafael C. Gonzalez, Richard E. Woods & Steven L. Eddins (2004) Digital Image Processing Using MATLAB, Pearson Education Ptd. Ltd, Singapore.
- [15] Ramadevi, Y & et al (2010) "[Segmentation and object recognition using edge detection techniques](#)", International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology, Vol 2, No.6, 153-161.
- [16] Roberts, L (1965) "Machine Perception of 3-D Solids", Optical and Electro-optical Information Processing, MIT Press.
- [17] Robinson. G (1977) "Edge detection by compass gradient masks", Computer graphics and image processing, 6, 492-501.
- [18] Rousseeuw, P. J & Leroy, A (1987) Robust Regression and outlier detection, John Wiley & Sons, New York.
- [19] Senthilkumaran. N & R. Rajesh (2009) "[Edge Detection Techniques for Image Segmentation – A Survey of Soft Computing Approaches](#)", International Journal of Recent Trends in Engineering, Vol. 1, No. 2, 250-254.
- [20] Sowmya. B & Sheelarani. B (2009) "Colour Image Segmentation Using Soft Computing Techniques", International Journal of Soft Computing Applications, Issue 4, 69-80.
- [21] Umesh Sehgal (2011) "[Edge detection techniques in digital image processing using Fuzzy Logic](#)", International Journal of Research in IT and Management, Vol.1, Issue 3, 61-66.
- [22] Yu, X, Bui, T.D. & et al. (1994) "[Robust Estimation for Range Image Segmentation and Reconstruction](#)", IEEE trans. Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, 16 (5), 530-538.

DIAGONAL BASED FEATURE EXTRACTION FOR HANDWRITTEN ALPHABETS RECOGNITION SYSTEM USING NEURAL NETWORK

J.Pradeep¹, E.Srinivasan² and S.Himavathi³

^{1,2} Department of ECE, Pondicherry College Engineering, Pondicherry, India.

³ Department of EEE, Pondicherry College Engineering, Pondicherry, India.

ABSTRACT

An off-line handwritten alphabetical character recognition system using multilayer feed forward neural network is described in the paper. A new method, called, diagonal based feature extraction is introduced for extracting the features of the handwritten alphabets. Fifty data sets, each containing 26 alphabets written by various people, are used for training the neural network and 570 different handwritten alphabetical characters are used for testing. The proposed recognition system performs quite well yielding higher levels of recognition accuracy compared to the systems employing the conventional horizontal and vertical methods of feature extraction. This system will be suitable for converting handwritten documents into structural text form and recognizing handwritten names

KEYWORDS

Handwritten character recognition, Image processing, Feature extraction, feed forward neural networks.

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/jcsit/0211jicsit03.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/jicsit2011_curr.html

REFERENCES

1. S. Mori, C.Y. Suen and K. Kamamoto, "Historical review of OCR research and development," Proc. of IEEE, vol. 80, pp. 1029-1058, July 1992.
2. S. Impedovo, L. Ottaviano and S. Occhinegro, "Optical character recognition", International Journal Pattern Recognition and Artificial Intelligence, Vol. 5(1-2), pp. 1- 24, 1991.
3. V.K. Govindan and A.P. Shivaprasad, "Character Recognition – A review," Pattern Recognition, vol. 23, no. 7, pp. 671- 683,
4. R. Plamondon and S. N. Srihari, "On-line and off- line handwritten character recognition: A comprehensive survey,"IEEE. Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 63-84, 2000.
5. N. Arica and F. Yarman-Vural, "An Overview of Character Recognition Focused on Off-line Handwriting", IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics, Part C: Applications and Reviews, 2001, 31(2), pp. 216 - 233.
6. U. Bhattacharya, and B. B. Chaudhuri, "Handwritten numeral databases of Indian Scripts and multistage recognition of mixed numerals," IEEE Transaction on Pattern analysis and machine intelligence, vol.31, No.3, pp.444-457, 2009.
7. U. Pal, T. Wakabayashi and F. Kimura, "Handwritten numeral recognition of six popular scripts," Ninth International conference on Document Analysis and Recognition ICDAR 07, Vol.2, pp.749-753, 200
8. R.G. Casey and E.Lecolinet, "A Survey of Methods and Strategies in Character Segmentation," IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, Vol. 18, No.7, July 1996, pp. 690-706.
9. Anil.K.Jain and Torfinn Taxt, "Feature extraction methods for character recognitionA Survey," Pattern Recognition, vol. 29, no. 4, pp. 641-662, 1996.
10. R.G. Casey and E.Lecolinet, "A Survey of Methods and Strategies in Character Segmentation," IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, Vol. 18, No.7, July 1996, pp. 690-706.
11. C. L. Liu, H. Fujisawa, "Classification and Learning for Character Recognition:Comparison of Methods and Remaining Problems", Int. Workshop on Neural Networks and Learning in Document Analysis and Recognition, Seoul, 2005.
12. F. Bortolozzi, A. S. Brito, Luiz S. Oliveira and M. Morita, "Recent Advances in Handwritten

Recognition”, Document Analysis, Umapada Pal, Swapan K. Parui, Bidyut B. Chaudhuri, pp 1-30.

13. Anita Pal & Dayashankar Singh, “Handwritten English Character Recognition Using Neural,” Network International Journal of Computer Science & Communication.vol. 1,No. 2, July-December 2010, pp. 141-144.

14. Dinesh Acharya U, N V Subba Reddy and Krishnamurthy, “Isolated handwritten Kannada numeral recognition using structural feature and K-means cluster,” IISN- 2007, pp-125 -129.

15. N. Sharma, U. Pal, F. Kimura, "Recognition of Handwritten Kannada Numerals", 9thInternational Conference on Information Technology (ICIT'06), ICIT, pp. 133- 136.

16. Rafael C. Gonzalez, Richard E. woods and Steven L.Eddins, Digital Image Processing using MATLAB, Pearson Education, Dorling Kindersley, South Asia, 2004.

17. S.V.Rajashekararadhya, and P.VanajaRanjan, “Efficient zone based feature extraction algorithm for handwritten numeral recognition of four popular south-Indian scripts,” Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology, JATIT vol.4, no.12, pp.1171-1181, 2008.

SECURITY THREATS ON CLOUD COMPUTING VULNERABILITIES

Te-Shun Chou

**Department of Technology Systems, East Carolina University, Greenville, NC,
U.S.A.**

ABSTRACT

Clouds provide a powerful computing platform that enables individuals and organizations to perform variety levels of tasks such as: use of online storage space, adoption of business applications, development of customized computer software, and creation of a “realistic” network environment. In previous years, the number of people using cloud services has dramatically increased and lots of data has been stored in cloud computing environments. In the meantime, data breaches to cloud services are also increasing every year due to hackers who are always trying to exploit the security vulnerabilities of the architecture of cloud. In this paper, three cloud service models were compared; cloud security risks and threats were investigated based on the nature of the cloud service models. Real world cloud attacks were included to demonstrate the techniques that hackers used against cloud computing systems. In addition, countermeasures to cloud security breaches are presented.

KEYWORDS

Cloud computing, cloud security threats and countermeasures, cloud service models

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/jcsit/5313ijcsit06.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit2013_curr.html

REFERENCES

1. DataLossDB Open Security Foundation. <http://datalossdb.org/statistics>
2. Sophos Security Threat Report 2012. <http://www.sophos.com/>
3. Amazon.com Server Said to Have Been Used in Sony Attack, May 2011. <http://www.bloomberg.com/news/2011-05-13/sony-network-said-to-have-been-invaded-by-hackersusing-amazon-com-server.html>
4. D. Jamil and H. Zaki, "[Security Issues in Cloud Computing and Countermeasures](#)," International Journal of Engineering Science and Technology, Vol. 3 No. 4, pp. 2672-2676, April 2011.
5. K. Zunnurhain and S. Vrbsky, "[Security Attacks and Solutions in Clouds](#)," 2nd IEEE International Conference on Cloud Computing Technology and Science, Indianapolis, December 2010.
6. W. A. Jansen, "Cloud Hooks: Security and Privacy Issues in Cloud Computing," 44th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences, pp. 1–10, Koloa, Hawaii, January 2011.
7. T. Roth, "[Breaking Encryptions Using GPU Accelerated Cloud Instances](#)," Black Hat Technical Security Conference, 2011.
8. CERT Coordination Center, Denial of Service. http://www.packetstormsecurity.org/distributed/denial_of_service.html
9. M. Jensen, J. Schwenk, N. Gruschka, and L. L. Iacono, "[On Technical Security Issues in Cloud Computing](#)," IEEE International Conference in Cloud Computing, pp. 109-116, Bangalore, 2009.
10. Thunder in the Cloud: \$6 Cloud-Based Denial-of-Service Attack, August 2010. http://blogs.computerworld.com/16708/thunder_in_the_cloud_6_cloud_based_denial_of_service_attack
11. DDoS Attack Rains Down on Amazon Cloud, October 2009. http://www.theregister.co.uk/2009/10/05/amazon_bitbucket_outage/
12. 2011 CyberSecurity Watch Survey, CERT Coordination Center at Carnegie Mellon University.
13. D. Catteddu and G. Hogben, "[Cloud Computing Benefits, Risks and Recommendations for Information Security](#)," The European Network and Information Security Agency (ENISA), November 2009.

14. Insider Threats Related to Cloud Computing, CERT, July 2012. <http://www.cert.org/>
15. Data Breach Trends & Stats, Symantec, 2012. <http://www.indefenseofdata.com/data-breach-trendsstats/>
16. 2012 Has Delivered Her First Giant Data Breach, January 2012. <http://www.infosecisland.com/blogview/19432-2012-Has-Delivered-Her-First-Giant-DataBreach.html>
17. A Few Wrinkles Are Etching Facebook, Other Social Sites, USA Today, 2011. http://www.usatoday.com/printedition/life/20090115/socialnetworking15_st.art.html
18. An Update on LinkedIn Member Passwords Compromised, LinkedIn Blog, June, 2012. <http://blog.linkedin.com/2012/06/06/linkedin-member-passwords-compromised/>
19. Dropbox: Yes, We Were Hacked, August 2012. <http://gigaom.com/cloud/dropbox-yes-we-werehacked/>
20. Web Based Attacks, Symantec White Paper, February 2009.
21. Symantec Internet Security Threat Report, 2011 Trends, Vol. 17, April 2012.
22. P. P. Ramgonda and R. R. Mudholkar, "[Cloud Market Cogitation and Techniques to Averting SQL Injection for University Cloud](#)," International Journal of Computer Technology and Applications, Vol. 3, No. 3, pp. 1217-1224, January, 2012.
23. A. S. Choudhary and M. L. Dhore, "[CIDT: Detection of Malicious Code Injection Attacks on Web Application](#)," International Journal of Computer Applications, Vol. 52, No. 2, pp. 19-26, August 2012.
24. Web Application Attack Report For The Second Quarter of 2012. <http://www.firehost.com/company/newsroom/web-application-attack-report-second-quarter-2012>
25. Visitors to Sony PlayStation Website at Risk of Malware Infection, July 2008. <http://www.sophos.com/en-us/press-office/press-releases/2008/07/playstation.aspx>
26. N. Provos, M. A. Rajab, and P. Mavrommatis, "Cybercrime 2.0: When the Cloud Turns Dark," ACM Communications, Vol. 52, No. 4, pp. 42–47, 2009.
27. S. S. Rajan, Cloud Security Series | SQL Injection and SaaS, Cloud Computing Journal, November 2010.

28. Researchers Demo Cloud Security Issue With Amazon AWS Attack, October 2011. http://www.pcworld.idg.com.au/article/405419/researchers_demo_cloud_security_issue_amazon_aws_attack/
29. M. McIntosh and P. Austel, "XML Signature Element Wrapping Attacks and Countermeasures," 2005 workshop on Secure web services, ACM Press, New York, NY, pp. 20–27, 2005.
30. N. Gruschka and L. L. Iacono, "[Vulnerable Cloud: SOAP Message Security Validation Revisited](#)," IEEE International Conference on Web Services, Los Angeles, 2009.
31. A. Tripathi and A. Mishra, "Cloud Computing Security Considerations Interface," 2011 IEEE International Conference on Signal Processing, Communications and Computing, Xi'an, China, September 2011.
32. H. C. Li, P. H. Liang, J. M. Yang, and S. J. Chen, "Analysis on Cloud-Based Security Vulnerability Assessment," IEEE International Conference on E-Business Engineering, pp.490-494, November 2010.
33. Amazon: Hey Spammers, Get Off My Cloud!http://voices.washingtonpost.com/securityfix/2008/07/amazon_hey_spammers_get_off_my.html
34. W. Jansen and T. Grance, "Guidelines on Security and Privacy in Public Cloud Computing," Computer Security Division, Information Technology Laboratory, National Institute of Standards and Technology, Special Publication 800-144, December 2011.
35. Tackling the Insider Threat <http://www.bankinfosecurity.com/blogs.php?postID=140>
36. "Cloud Security Risks and Solutions," White Paper, BalaBit IT Security, July 2010.
37. S. J. Stolfo, M. B. Salem, and A. D. Keromytis, "Fog computing: Mitigating Insider Data Theft Attacks in the Cloud," IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy Workshops, pp. 125-128, San Francisco, CA, 2012.
38. M. Jensen, C. Meyer, J. Somorovsky, and J. Schwenk, "On the Effectiveness of XML Schema Validation for Countering XML Signature Wrapping Attacks," First International Workshop on Securing Services on the Cloud, Milan, Italy, September 2011.
39. S. Gajek, M. Jensen, L. Liao, and J. Schwenk, "Analysis of Signature Wrapping Attacks and Countermeasures," IEEE International Conference on Web Services, pp. 575–582, Miami, Florida, July 2009.

COMMON PHASES OF COMPUTER FORENSICS INVESTIGATION MODELS

Yunus Yusoff, Roslan Ismail and Zainuddin Hassan

**College of Information Technology, Universiti Tenaga Nasional,
Selangor, Malaysia**

ABSTRACT

The increasing criminal activities using digital information as the means or targets warrant for a structured manner in dealing with them. Since 1984 when a formalized process been introduced, a great number of new and improved computer forensic investigation processes have been developed. In this paper, we reviewed a few selected investigation processes that have been produced throughout the years and then identified the commonly shared processes. Hopefully, with the identification of the commonly shard process, it would make it easier for the new users to understand the processes and also to serve as the basic underlying concept for the development of a new set of processes. Based on the commonly shared processes, we proposed a generic computer forensics investigation model, known as GCFIM.

KEYWORDS

Computer Forensic Models, Computer Forensic Investigation

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/jcsit/0611csit02.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/jicsit2011_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] M. G. Noblett, M. M. Pollitt & L. A. Presley, (2000) "Recovering and Examining Computer Forensic Evidence", *Forensic Science Communications*, Vol. 2, No. 4.
- [2] M. M. Pollitt, (1995) "Computer Forensics: An Approach to Evidence in Cyberspace", in *Proceeding of the National Information Systems Security Conference*, Baltimore, MD, Vol. II, pp. 487-491.
- [3] M. M. Pollitt, (2007) "An Ad Hoc Review of Digital Forensic Models", in *Proceeding of the Second International Workshop on Systematic Approaches to Digital Forensic Engineering (SADFE'07)*, Washington, USA.
- [4] G. Palmer, (2001) "DTR-T001-01 Technical Report. A Road Map for Digital Forensic Research", *Digital Forensics Workshop (DFRWS)*, Utica, New York.
- [5] M. Reith, C. Carr & G. Gunsh, (2002) "An Examination of Digital Forensics Models", *International Journal of Digital Evidence*, Vol. 1, No. 3.
- [6] B. Carrier & E. H. Spafford, (2003) "Getting Physical with the Digital Investigation Process", *International Journal of Digital Evidence*, Vol. 2, No. 2
- [7] V. Baryamereeba & F. Tushabe, (2004) "The Enhanced Digital Investigation Process Model", in *Proceeding of Digital Forensic Research Workshop*, Baltimore, MD.
- [8] M. K. Rogers, J. Goldman, R. Mislán, T. Wedge & S. Debrotá, (2006) "Computer Forensic Field Triage Process Model", presented at the *Conference on Digital Forensics, Security and Law*, pp. 27-40.
- [9] P. Sundresan, (2009) "Digital Forensic Model based on Malaysian Investigation Process", *International Journal of Computer Science and Network Security*, Vol. 9, No. 8.
- [10] S. Ciardhuain, (2004) "An Extended Model of Cybercrime Investigation", *International Journal of Digital Evidence*, Vol. 3, No. 1, pp. 1-22.
- [11] P. Stephenson, (2003) "A Comprehensive Approach to Digital Incident Investigation.", *Information Security Technical Report*, Vol. 8, Issue 2, pp 42-52. *International Journal of Computer Science & Information Technology (IJCSIT)*, Vol 3, No 3, June 2011 31
- [12] N. L. Beebe & J. G. Clark, (2004) "A Hierarchical, Objective-Based Framework for the Digital Investigations Process", in *Proceeding of Digital Forensic Research Workshop (DFRWS)*, Baltimore, Maryland.
- [13] M. Kohn, J. H. P. Eloff, & M. S. Olivier, (2006) "Framework for a Digital Forensic Investigation", in *Proceedings of the ISSA 2006 from Insight to Foresight Conference*, Sandton, South Africa.
- [14] F. C. Freiling & B. Schwittay, (2007) "Common Process Model for Incident and Computer Forensics", in *Proceedings of Conference on IT Incident Management and IT Forensics*, Stuttgart, Germany, pp. 19-40.
- [15] D. Bem & E. Huebner, (2007) "Computer Forensic Analysis in a Virtual Environment", *International Journal of Digital Evidence*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 1-13.
- [16] E. S. Pilli, R. C. Joshi, & R. Niyogi, (2010) "Network Forensic frameworks: Survey and research challenges," *Digital Investigation*, Vol. 7, pp. 14-27

**HYBRID OF PARTICLE SWARM OPTIMIZATION WITH
EVOLUTIONARY OPERATORS TO FRAGILE IMAGE
WATERMARKING BASED DCT**

**Sawsan Morkos Gharghory Computers and Systems Department, Electronics Research Institute,
Cairo, Egypt**

ABSTRACT

Particle swarm optimization (PSO) is a new promising evolutionary algorithm for the optimization and search problem. One problem of PSO is its tendency to trap into local optima due to its mechanism in information sharing. This paper proposes a novel hybrid PSO, namely (HPSO) technique by merging both a mutation operator and natural selection to solve the problem of premature convergence. By introducing Cauchy mutation and evolutionary selection strategy based on roulette wheel selection, HPSO could greatly reduce the probability of trapping into local optimum. HPSO is proposed to improve the performance of fragile watermarking based DCT which results in enhancing both the quality of the watermarked image and the extracted watermark. After embedding watermark to the original image in the frequency domain, the conversion of real numbers of the modified coefficients in frequency domain to integer numbers in spatial domain produces some rounding errors problem. This problem results in completely different of the extracted watermark from the embedded watermark. The new developed PSO with evolutionary operators is carried out for correcting the rounding errors by training a translation map used to modify the inverse DCT (IDCT) coefficients from real to integer numbers. The experimental results show the superiority of the proposed algorithm comparing with the standard PSO for improving the performance of DCT fragile watermarking. Besides, it has been shown that the developed PSO is faster in convergence and the obtained results proved to have higher fitness than the other algorithm.

KEYWORDS

Particle Swarm Optimization, Evolutionary Operators, DCT fragile watermarking

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/jcsit/0611csit10.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/jcsit2011_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] F.A.P. Petitcolas, R.J. Anderson, M.G. Kuhn, "Information hiding—a survey", Proc. IEEE 87 (7) (1999) 1062–1078.
- [2] F Hartung & M Kutter, Multimedia Watermarking Techniques, Proc IEEE, vol 87, no 7, pp 1079-1107, July 1999.
- [3] D. Artz, "Digital Steganography: Hiding data within data," IEEE Internet Computing, vol.5,pp. 75- 80, May-June 2001.
- [4] M. Kankanhalli and K. Ramakrishnan “Adaptive visible watermarking of images” Proc. IEEE Intl. Conf. Multimedia Comp. and Sys., vol.1, pp. 568-573, 1999.
- [5] Yeung, M. M. Mintzer, F. “An Invisible Watermarking Technique for image Verification” Proc. of ICIP 1997, Santa Barbara, CA, pp. 680-682.
- [6] J.S. Pan, H.C. Huang, L.C. Jain, “Intelligent Watermarking Techniques”, World scientific Publishing Company, Singapore, 2004.
- [7] N. Nikolaidis, I. Pitas, "Robust image watermarking in the spatial domain", Signal Process. 66, 1998 pp. 385–403.
- [8] C.I. Podilchuk, W.J. Zeng, "Image-adaptive watermarking using visual models", IEEE Trans. on Selected Areas in Communications, vol. 16, pp. 525–539, 1998. ...
- [9] R. Schyndel, A. Tirkel, C. Osborne, in: Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Image Processing, Austin, Texas, 1994, p. 86.
- [10] J. Fridrich, M. Goljan, A. Baldoza, in: Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Image Processing, Vancouver, Canada, 2000, p. 446.
- [11] E.T. Lin, E.J. Delp, in: Proceedings of the ACM Multimedia and Security Workshop, Orlando, 1999, p. 25.
- [12] R.S. Alomari, A. Al-Jaber, Int. J. Comput. Inform. Sci. 2 (2005) 27. [13] C. T. Hsu, J. L. Wu, "Hidden digital watermarks in images" Image Processing, IEEE Transactions on Volume: 8 1 , Jan. 1999 , Page(s): 58 -68
- [14] J.R. Hernandez, M. Amado, F. Perez-Gonzalez, "DCT-domain watermarking techniques for still images: detector performance analysis and a new structure", IEEE Trans. Image Process. 9 (1) 2000, pp. 55–68.
- [15] W.C. Chu, "DCT-based image watermarking using sub-sampling", IEEE Trans. Multimedia 5 (1) 2003, pp 34–38.
- [16] C.C. Chen, De.S.Kao, "DCT-Based Zero Replacement Reversible Image Watermarking Approach", International Journal of Innovative, Computer, Information and Control, Vol. 4, Num.11, pp. 3027, November 2008.
- [17] G. Zhu, N. Sang, "Watermarking Algorithm Research and Implementation Based on DCT Block", Proceedings of World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology, Vol. 35, ISSN 2070-3740, November 2008. C.T. Li, H. Si, J. Electron. Imaging 16 (2007). 013009-1-9.

- [18] M. Barni, F. Bartolini, A. Piva, "Improved wavelet-based watermarking through pixel-wise masking", *Image Process. IEEE Trans. Image Process.* 10 (5), 2001, pp. 783–791.
- [19] E. Ganic, A. Eskiciog̃lu, in: *Proceedings of the ACM Multimedia and Security Workshop, Magdeburg, Germany, 2004*, p. 166.
- [20] F.Y. Shih, Y.T. Wu, *J. Vis. Commun. Image Representation* 16 (2005) 115.
- [21] C.C. Chang, Y.C. Chang, J.J. Shen, in: *International Conference on Intelligent Information Hiding and Multimedia Signal Processing, IHH-MSP '06, 2006*, p. 453. *International Journal of Computer Science & Information Technology (IJCSIT)*, Vol 3, No 3, June 2011 156
- [22] V. Aslantas, S. Ozer, S. Ozturk, "Improving the Performance of DCT-based Fragile Watermarking using Intelligent Optimization Algorithms" *optics communication*, issue(14), pp.2806-2817, July 2009.
- [23] Yi-Tung Kao and Erwie Zahara, "A hybrid genetic algorithm and particle swarm optimization for multimodal functions", *Applied Soft Computing* Vol. 8, pp 849-857, 2008.
- [24] Robinson, J., Sinton, S., and Rahmat-Samii, Y., "Particle swarm, genetic algorithm, and their hybrids: optimization of a profiled corrugated horn antenna", *IEEE International Symposium on Antennas & Propagation. San Antonio, Texas. June, 2002*.
- [25] H. A. Kamal, "A new integrated GA/PSO Algorithm for Optimal tuning of PID Controller", *the Mediterranean Journal of Measurement and Control*, Vol. 6, No. 1, pp.18-24, January 2010.
- [26] M. Rashid and A. Rauf Baig, "A genetic programming based adaptable evolutionary hybrid particle swarm optimization algorithm", *International Journal of Innovative Computing, Information and Control (ICIC)*, Vol. 6, Nu. 1, January 2010.
- [27] Angeline, P. J., "Using selection to improve particle swarm optimization", *Proceedings of the IEEE Congress on Evolutionary Computation (CEC 1998)*, Anchorage, Alaska, USA. 1998.
- [28] Løvbjerg, M., Rasmussen, T., and Krink, T, "Hybrid particle swarm optimizer with breeding and subpopulations", *Proceedings of the third Genetic and Evolutionary Computation Conference (GECCO)*, Vol. 1, pp. 469-476, 2001.
- [29] A. Ratnaweera, S. K. Halgamuge, and H. C. Watson, Self-organizing hierarchical particle swarm optimizer with time-varying acceleration coefficients, *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 8,no. 3, pp. 240–255, 2004.
- [30] Miranda, V., and Fonseca, N., "New evolutionary particle swarm algorithm (EPSO) applied to voltage/VAR control", *The 14th Power Systems Computation Conference (PSCC'02)*, Seville, Spain, June, 2002.
- [31] Løvbjerg, M., and Krink, T., "Extending particle swarms with self-organized criticality", *Proceedings of the Fourth Congress on Evolutionary Computation (CEC-2002)*.
- [32] Blackwell, T., and Bentley, P. J., (2002). "Don't push me! Collision-avoiding swarms". *IEEE Congress on Evolutionary Computation, Honolulu, Hawaii USA, 2002*.
- [33] J. Sun, B. Feng, W. Xu, Particle swarm optimization with particles having quantum behavior, in *Proceedings of the IEEE Congress on Evolutionary Computation, Portland, Oregon USA*, pp. 325-331, 2004.

- [34] Jing Liu, Wenbo Xu, Jun Sun, Quantum-behaved particle swarm optimization with mutation operator. Proceedings of the 17th IEEE International Conference on Tools with Artificial Intelligence Pages: 237 - 240 , 2005
- [35] R. A. Krohling, Gaussian particle swarm with jumps, in Proceedings of the IEEE Congress on Evolutionary Computation, Edinburgh, UK, pp. 1226-1231, 2005.
- [36] R. A. Krohling, L. dos Santos Coelho, PSO-E: Particle Swarm with Exponential Distribution, in Proceedings of the IEEE Congress on Evolutionary Computation, pp1428- 1433, July 2006.
- [37] H. Narihisa, T. Taniguchi, M. Ohta, and K. Katayama, Evolutionary Programming with Exponential Mutation, in Proceedings of the IASTED Artificial Intelligence and soft Computing, Benidorn, Spain, pp. 55-50, 2005.
- [38] J. Kennedy, R.C. Eberhart, in: Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Neural Networks, Australia, 1995, p. 1942.
- [39] X. Yao, Y. Liu, G. Lin, "Evolutionary programming made faster" IEEE Trans. Evolutionary Computation 1999; 3(2); 82-102. [40] Y.H. Kim, H. Song, H.J. Kang, Lect. Note Artificial. Intelligence 2682(2005) 560.

CITATION COUNT – 140

**SEGMENTATION AND OBJECT RECOGNITION USING EDGE DETECTION
TECHNIQUES**

**Y.Ramadevi, T.Sridevi, B.Poornima, B.Kalyani Department of CSE , Chaitanya Bharathi
Institute of Technology Gandipet, Hyderabad.**

ABSTRACT

Image segmentation is to partition an image into meaningful regions with respect to a particular application. Object recognition is the task of finding a given object in an image or video sequence. In this paper, interaction between image segmentation (using different edge detection methods) and object recognition are discussed. Edge detection methods such as Sobel, Prewitt, Roberts, Canny, Laplacian of Guassian(LoG) are used for segmenting the image. Expectation-Maximization (EM) algorithm, OSTU and Genetic algorithms were used to demonstrate the synergy between the segmented images and object recognition.

KEYWORDS

EM algorithm, OSTU, Genetic Algorithm, Image Segmentation, Object Recognition.

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/icsit/1210jicsit14.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/icsit2010_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] Iasonas Kokkinos, and Petros Maragos (2009), "Synergy between Object Recognition and image segmentation using Expectation and Maximization Algorithm"., IEEE Trans. on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence (PAMI), Vol. 31(8), pp. 1486-1501, 2009.
- [2] Wen-Xiong Kang, Qing-Qiang Yang, Run-Peng Liang (2009), "The Comparative Research on Image Segmentation Algorithms," First International Workshop on Education Technology and Computer Science.
- [3] V. Ferrari, T. Tuytelaars, and L.V. Gool(2004), "Simultaneous Object Recognition and Segmentation by Image Exploration," Proc. Eighth European Conf. Computer Vision, 2004.
- [4] B. Leibe, A. Leonardis, and B. Schiele(2004), "Combined Object Categorization and Segmentation with an Implicit Shape Model," Proc. ECCV Workshop Statistical Learning in Computer Vision, 2004.
- [5] Y.Ramadevi, B.Kalyani, T.Sridevi(2010), " Synergy between Object Recognition and Image Segmentation", International Journal on Computer Science and Engineering, Vol. 02, No. 08, 2010, 2767-2772.
- [6] N.Senthilkumarn, R.Rajesh(2009), "Edge Detection Techniques for Image Segmentation- A Survey of Soft Computing Approaches", IJRTE, vol1,No2, 2009 250-254.

UBIQUITOUS MOBILE HEALTH MONITORING SYSTEM FOR ELDERLY (UMHMSE)

**Abderrahim BOUROUIS¹, Mohamed FEHAM² and Abdelhamid
BOUCHACHIA³**

¹STIC laboratory, Abou-bekr BELKAID University, Tlemcen, Algeria

²STIC laboratory, Abou-bekr BELKAID University, Tlemcen, Algeria

**³Research Group, Software Engineering and Soft Computing, University of
Klagenfurt, Austria**

ABSTRACT

Recent research in ubiquitous computing uses technologies of Body Area Networks (BANs) to monitor the person's kinematics and physiological parameters. In this paper we propose a real time mobile health system for monitoring elderly patients from indoor or outdoor environments. The system uses a biosignal sensor worn by the patient and a Smartphone as a central node. The sensor data is collected and transmitted to the intelligent server through GPRS/UMTS to be analyzed. The prototype (UMHMSE) monitors the elderly mobility, location and vital signs such as SpO₂ and Heart Rate. Remote users (family and medical personnel) might have a real time access to the collected information through a web application.

KEYWORDS

Ubiquitous health monitoring, Mobile Health Monitoring, Smartphone. Intelligent central sever,

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/icsit/0611csit06.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/iicsit2011_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] CN Scanail, B Ahearne and GM Lyons, "Long-Term Telemonitoring of Mobility Trends of Elderly People Using SMS Messaging", IEEE Communications, 2006.
- [2] <http://www.ons.dz/index-en.php>
- [3] World Health Organization 2010, WORLD HEALTH STATISTICS 2010
- [4] Phillip Olla and Joseph Tan, "Mobile Health Solutions for Biomedical Applications", Medical inforMation science reference, 2009, pp. 129-140.
- [5] Shimizu, K , "Telemedicine by Mobile Communication", IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology, 1999, pp. 32-44.
- [6] C. N. Scanail , S. Carew ,P. Barralon, N. Noury , D. Lyons and G. M. Lyons, "A review of approaches to mobility telemonitoring of the elderly in their living environment", Annals of Biomedical Engineering, 2006,vol. 34, pp. 545-565.
- [7] E. Jovanov , A. Milenkovic, C. Otto and P. C. De Groen, "A wireless body area network of intelligent motionsensors for computer assisted physical rehabilitation" , Journal of NeuroEngineering and Rehabilitation, 2005, vol. 2.
- [8] A Van Halteren , R Bults ,K Wac , D Konstantas , I Widya , N Dokovsky , G Koprnikov , V Jones and R Herzog " Mobile Patient Monitoring: The MobiHealth System" ,The Journal on Information Technology in Healthcare 2004; 2(5); pp. 365–373.
- [9] D Konstantas , A Van Halteren¹,R Bults , K Wac , V Jones , I Widya and R Herzog, " MOBIHEALTH : AMBULANT PATIENT MONITORING OVER PUBLIC WIRELESS NETWORKS ", Mediterranean Conference on Medical and Biological Engineering MEDICON 2004.
- [10] J. M. Choi, B. H. Choi, J. W. Seo ,R. H. Sohn, M. S. Ryu and W. Yi,A, "System for Ubiquitous Health Monitoring in the Bedroom via a Bluetooth Network and Wireless LAN". Proc. The 26th Annual International Conference of the IEEE EMBS, San Fransisco, CA, USA: Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society, vol. 2, 2004, pp. 3362-3365.
- [11] E. Farella, A. Pieracci , D. Brunelli , L. Benini , B. Ricco and A. Acquaviva, "Design and implementation of WiMoCA node for a body area wireless sensor network," in Proceedings of the 2005 Systems Communications, 2005, pp. 342-347.
- [12] M. J. Morón ,J. R. Luque , A. A. Botella , E. J. Cuberos ,E. Casilari and A. Diaz- Estrella, "A Smart Phone-based Personal Area Network for Remote Monitoring of Biosignals", 4th International Workshop on Wearable and Implantable Body Sensor Networks (BSN 2007) IFMBE Proceedings, 2007, Volume 13, 3rd Session, pp. 116-121.

- [13] S. Dai and Y. Zhang ,”Wireless Physiological Multi-parameter Monitoring System Based on Mobile Communication Networks”, In 19th IEEE Symposium on Computer- Based Medical Systems Based on Mobile Communication Networks, Washington, DC, USA: IEEE Computer Soceity, , 2006, pp. 473-478.
- [14] J. W. Lee and J. Y. Jung , “ ZigBee Device Design and Implementation for Context- Aware UHealthcare System”,The IEEE 2nd International Conference on Systems and Networks Communications, Cap Esterel, French Riviera, 2007, IEEE Computer Society, pp. 22.
- [15] Guang-Zhong Yang , “Body Sensor Networks” (Ed) Springer; 1st Edition. 2006, pp.147-149. [16] M. J. Morón , J. R. Luque , A. A. Botella , E. J. Cuberos , E. Casilari , A. Diaz-Estrella and J. A. Gázquez , “Development of wireless Body Area Network based on J2ME for M-Health applications”, 2nd European Computing Conference , 2008.
- [17] N. Deblauwe and L. V. Biesen, "An event-driven lbs for public transport: design and feasibility study of gsm-based positioning," in Proceedings of the 45th FICE congress Athens, 2005, pp. 29-35.
- [18] Nonin Medical ,<http://www.nonin.com/>
- [19] http://www.forum.nokia.com/Devices/Device_specifications.
- [20] M. J. Morón, J. R. Luque, A. Gómez-Jaime, E. Casilari, and A. Díaz-Estrella, “Prototyping of a remote monitoring system for a medical Personal Area Network using Python,” in 3rd International Conference on Pervasive Computing Technologies for Healthcare, 2009.PervasiveHealth pp. 1 –5.
- [21] <http://wiki.forum.nokia.com/index.php/Category:Python>
- [22] M Saipunidzam, I Mohammad Noor and M.T Shakirah , “M-LEARNING: A NEW PARADIGM OF LEARNING MATHEMATICS IN MALAYSIA”,

**MACHINE LEARNING METHODS FOR SPAM E-MAIL
CLASSIFICATION**

W.A. Awad¹ and S.M. ELseuofi²

1Math.&Comp.Sci.Dept., Science faculty, Port Said University

2Inf. System Dept.,Ras El Bar High inst.

ABSTRACT

The increasing volume of unsolicited bulk e-mail (also known as spam) has generated a need for reliable anti-spam filters. Machine learning techniques now days used to automatically filter the spam e-mail in a very successful rate. In this paper we review some of the most popular machine learning methods (Bayesian classification, k-NN, ANNs, SVMs, Artificial immune system and Rough sets) and of their applicability to the problem of spam Email classification. Descriptions of the algorithms are presented, and the comparison of their performance on the SpamAssassin spam corpus is presented.

KEYWORDS

Spam, E-mail classification, Machine learning algorithms

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/jcsit/0211jcsit12.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit2011_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] M. N. Marsono, M. W. El-Kharashi, and F. Gebali, "Binary LNS-based naïve Bayes inference engine for spam control: Noise analysis and FPGA synthesis", IET Computers & Digital Techniques, 2008
- [2] Muhammad N. Marsono, M. Watheq El-Kharashi, Fayez Gebali "Targeting spam control on middleboxes: Spam detection based on layer-3 e-mail content classification" Elsevier Computer Networks, 2009
- [3] Yuchun Tang, Sven Krasser, Yuanchen He, Weilai Yang, Dmitri Alperovitch "Support Vector Machines and Random Forests Modeling for Spam Senders Behavior Analysis" IEEE GLOBECOM, 2008
- [4] Guzella, T. S. and Caminhas, W. M. "A review of machine learning approaches to Spam filtering." Expert Syst. Appl., 2009
- [5] Wu, C. "Behavior-based spam detection using a hybrid method of rule-based techniques and neural networks" Expert Syst., 2009
- [6] Khorsi. "An overview of content-based spam filtering techniques", Informatica, 2007
- [7] Hao Zhang, Alexander C. Berg, Michael Maire, and Jitendra Malic. "SVM-KNN: Discriminative nearest neighbour classification for visual category recognition", IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, 2006
- [8] Carpinteiro, O. A. S., Lima, I., Assis, J. M. C., de Souza, A. C. Z., Moreira, E. M., & Pinheiro, C. A. M. "A neural model in anti-spam systems.", Lecture notes in computer science. Berlin, Springer, 2006
- [9] El-Sayed M. El-Alfy, Radwan E. Abdel-Aal "Using GMDH-based networks for improved spam detection and email feature analysis" Applied Soft Computing, Volume 11, Issue 1, January 2011
- [10] Li, K. and Zhong, Z., "Fast statistical spam filter by approximate classifications", In Proceedings of the Joint international Conference on Measurement and Modeling of Computer Systems. Saint Malo, France, 2006
- [11] Cormack, Gordon. Smucker, Mark. Clarke, Charles " Efficient and effective spam filtering and re-ranking for large web datasets" Information Retrieval, Springer Netherlands. January 2011
- [12] Almeida, tiago. Almeida, Jurandy. Yamakami, Akebo " Spam filtering: how the dimensionality reduction affects the accuracy of Naive Bayes classifiers" Journal of Internet Services and Applications, Springer London , February 2011
- [13] Yoo, S., Yang, Y., Lin, F., and Moon, I. "Mining social networks for personalized email prioritization". In Proceedings of the 15th ACM SIGKDD international Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining (Paris, France), June 28 - July 01, 2009

**ENHANCEMENT OF IMAGES USING MORPHOLOGICAL
TRANSFORMATIONS**

**K.Sreedhar¹ and B.Panlal² ¹Department of Electronics and communication Engineering,
VITS (N9) Karimnagar, Andhra Pradesh, India**

**²Department of Electronics and communication Engineering, VCE (S4) Karimnagar,
Andhra Pradesh, India**

ABSTRACT

This paper deals with enhancement of images with poor contrast and detection of background. Proposes a frame work which is used to detect the background in images characterized by poor contrast. Image enhancement has been carried out by the two methods based on the Weber's law notion. The first method employs information from image background analysis by blocks, while the second transformation method utilizes the opening operation, closing operation, which is employed to define the multi-background gray scale images. The complete image processing is done using MATLAB simulation model. Finally, this paper is organized as follows as Morphological transformation and Weber's law. Image background approximation to the background by means of block analysis in conjunction with transformations that enhance images with poor lighting. The multibackground notion is introduced by means of the opening by reconstruction shows a comparison among several techniques to improve contrast in images. Finally, conclusions are presented.

KEYWORDS

Image Background Analysis by blocks, Morphological Methods, Weber's law notion, Opening Operation, Closing Operation, Erosion-Dilation method, Block Analysis for Gray level images.

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/icsit/0212csit03.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/icsit2012_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1]. I. R. Terol-Villalobos, "A multiscale contrast approach on Morphological connected contrast mappings" *Opt. Eng.*, vol. 43, no. 7, pp. 1577–1595, 2009.
- [2]. J. Kasperek, "Real time morphological image contrast enhancement in FPGA," in *LNCS*, New York: Springer, 2008. [3]. I.R. Terol-Villalobos, "Morphological image enhancement and segmentation with analysis," P. W. Hawkes, Ed. New York: Academic, 2005, pp. 207–273.
- [4]. F. Meyer and J. Serra, "Contrast and Activity Lattice," *Signal Processing*, vol. 16, pp. 303–317, 1989.
- [5]. J. D. Mendiola-Santibañez and I. R. Terol-Villalobos, "Morphological contrast mappings based on the flat zone notion," vol. 6, pp. 25–37, 2005.
- [6]. A. Toet, "Multiscale contrast enhancement with applications to image fusion," *Opt. Eng.*, vol. 31, no. 5, 1992.
- [7]. S. Mukhopadhyay and B. Chanda, "A multiscale morphological approach to local contrast enhancement," *Signal Process.* vol. 80, no. 4, pp. 685–696, 2000.
- [8]. A. K. Jain, *Fundamentals of Digital Images Processing*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall, 1989.
- [9]. J. Short, J. Kittler, and K. Messer, "A comparison of photometric normalization algorithms for face verification," presented at the *IEEE Int. Conf. Automatic Face and Gesture Recognition*, 2004.
- [10]. C. R. González and E. Woods, *Digital Image Processing*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall, 1992.
- [11]. R. H. Sherrier and G. A. Johnson, "Regionally adaptive histogram equalization of the chest," *IEEE Trans. Med. Imag.*, vol. MI-6, pp. 1–7, 1987.
- [12]. A. Majumder and S. Irani, "Perception-based contrast enhancement of images," *ACM Trans. Appl. Percpt.*, vol. 4, no. 3, 2007, Article 17. *International Journal of Computer Science & Information Technology (IJCSIT)* Vol 4, No 1, Feb 2012 50
- [13]. Z. Liu, C. Zhang, and Z. Zhang, "Learning-based perceptual image quality improvement for video conferencing," presented at the *IEEE Int. Conf. Multimedia and Expo (ICME)*, Beijing, China, Jul. 2007.
- [14]. E. H. Weber, "De pulsu, resorptione, audita et tactu," in *Annotationes anatomicae et physiologicae*. Leipzig, Germany: Koehler, 1834.
- [15]. J. Serra and P. Salembier, "Connected operators and pyramids," presented at the *SPIE. Image Algebra and Mathematical Morphology*, San Diego, CA, Jul. 1993.
- [16]. P. Salembier and J. Serra, "Flat zones filtering, connected operators and filters by reconstruction," *IEEE Trans. Image Process.*, vol. 3, no.8, pp. 1153–1160, Aug. 1995.

**INFORMATION SECURITY RISK ANALYSIS METHODS AND
RESEARCH TRENDS: AHP AND FUZZY COMPREHENSIVE**

Method Ming-Chang Lee National Kaohsiung University of Applied Science, Taiwan

ABSTRACT

Information security risk analysis becomes an increasingly essential component of organization's operations. Traditional Information security risk analysis is quantitative and qualitative analysis methods. Quantitative and qualitative analysis methods have some advantages for information risk analysis. However, hierarchy process has been widely used in security assessment. A future research direction may be development and application of soft computing such as rough sets, grey sets, fuzzy systems, generic algorithm, support vector machine, and Bayesian network and hybrid model. Hybrid model are developed by integrating two or more existing model. A Practical advice for evaluation information security risk is discussed. This approach is combination with AHP and Fuzzy comprehensive method.

KEYWORDS

Information security risk analysis; quantitative risk assessment methods; qualitative risk assessment method; Analytical Hierarchy Process; soft computing

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/icsit/6114iicsit03.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/icsit2014_curr.html

REFERENCES

1. Alberts C, Dorofee A. (2002) "Managing Information Security Risks: The Octave Approach", Addison-Wesley Professional.2002.
2. Altuzarra A. Moreno-Jimnez, J. M, Salvador M. (2007), "A Bayesian prioritization procedure for AHP-group decision making". European Journal of Operation Research, Vol.18, No. 1, pp. 367-82.
3. Award, G.. A., Suitan E, Ahmad, N, Ithnan, N, Beg, A. H. (2011), "Multi-objective model to process security risk assessment based on AHP-PSO", Modern Applied Science, Vol. 5, No. 3, pp. 246-20.
4. Barber B, Davey J. (1992) "The use of the CCTA risk analysis and management methodology" CRAMM. MEDINF092, North Holland, pp. 1589-1593.
5. Baskerville R. (1993), "An analysis survey of information system security design methods: Implications for Information Systems Development". ACM Computing Survey, pp. 375-414.
6. Behnia A, Rahsid R. A, Chaudhry J. A. (2012), "A survey of information security risk analysis methods", Smart Computing Review, Vol. 2, No. 1, pp 79-93.
7. Bialas A. (2006), Security of information and services in modern institution and company (in Polish), WNT, Warsaw 2006. 8. Bodin L. D, Gordon L. A, Loeb M. P. (2005), "Evaluation information security investments using analytic hierarchy process". Communications of the ACM, Vol. 48, No. 2, pp. 78-83.
9. Boroushaki , S. and Malczewski, J., (2008), "Implementing an extension of the analytical hierarchy", process using ordered weighted averaging operators with fuzzy quantifiers in ArcGIS, Computer and Geosciences, 34, pp. 399-410
10. Chang, P. T., Hung K, C. (2005), "Applying the fuzzy weighted average approach to evaluation network security systems". Computers and Mathematics with Application, Vol. 49, pp. 1797-1814.
11. Chen A, Wang X. H, Huang H. (2004), "Research on multi-attribute information security risk assessment method based on threat analysis". Computer Engineering and Design, Vol. 30, No. 1, pp. 38-40.
12. CMS. CMS information security risk assessment methodology. CENT MEDIMED MEDICAID SERV 2009, Vol. 1, No. 1, pp.1-20.
13. Elky S. (2006), "An introduction to information system risk management". SANS institute InfoSec reading Room. 2006.
14. Eren-Dogu Z. F. Celikoglu C. C. (2011), Information security risk assessment: Bayesian prioritization for AHP group decision making". International Journal Innovation Computer Information Control, Vol. 8, No.11, pp. 8019-32.
15. Feng N, Li M. (2011), "An information systems security risk assessment model under uncertain environment". Applied Soft Computer, Vol. 11, No.7, pp. 4332-4340.
16. Feng N. and Yu, X., A (2012), "Data-driven assessment model for information system security risk management", Journal of Computers, Vol. 7, No.12, pp. 3103-3109.
17. Fredriksen R, Kristiansen M, Gran, B. A, Stolen K, Oppurud T. A, Dimitrakos T. (2002), The CORAS framework for a model-based risk management process. In the Proceeding of the 21th

International Conference on Computer Safety, Reliability and Security, 2002.

18. Fu S, Xiao Y. (2012), "Strengthening the research for Information security risk assessment". International Conference on Biological and Biomedical Science Advanced in Biomedical Engineering, Vol. 9; pp. 386-392.
19. Gao Y, Luo J. Z. (2009), Information security risk assessment based on grey relational decision making algorithm", Journal of Southeast University, Vol. 39, No. 2, pp. 225-229.
20. Goel S, Chen V. Information security risk analysis - a matrix-based approach. University at Albany, SUNY, 2005.
21. Guan B, Lo C, Wang P, Hwang J. Evaluation of information security related risks of an organizationthe application of the multi-criteria decision making method. In the Proceeding of IEEE the 37th Annual International Camahan Conference on Security, 2003, p. 168-75.
22. Hoffer J. A, George J. E, Valacich J. S. (1999), "Modern systems analysis& design". AddisonWesley-Longman. New York, N.Y., USA; 1999.
23. IST. A brief history of CORA, International Security Technology Inc (IST Inc.). 2002. <http://www.ist-usa.com> Accessed 16-6-2013.
24. Karabacaka B, Songukpinar I., (2005), "ISRAM: Information security risk analysis method", Computer & Security, March, pp. 147-169.
25. Keramati A, Yousefi N. (2011), "A proposes classification of data mining techniques in credit scoring". In the Proceeding of 2011 International Conference of Industrial Engineering and Operations Management, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, Jurnal 2011, pp. 22-4.
26. Liu F, Dai K, Wang Z. Y. (2004), "Research on the technology of quantitative security evaluation based on fuzzy number arithmetic operation", Fuzzy Systems and Mathematics, Vol. 18, No. 4, pp. 51- 54.
27. Liu Y, Lin Q, Meng K.(2010), "Research on quantitative security risk assessment method of an enterprise information system based on information entropy", Computer Science, Vol. 37, No. 5, pp. 45-48.
28. Lo C. C, Chen W. J. (2012), "A hybrid information security risk assessment procedure considering interdependences between controls", Expert Systems with Applications, Vol. 39, pp. 247-257.
29. Loch K. D, Carr H. H, Warkentin M. E. (1992), "Threats to information systems: today's reality, yesterday understands". MIS Quarterly, Vol. 16, No. 2, pp.173-186.
30. NIST Sp 800-30, sp800 30ri.pdf, Step. 2012. http://csrc.nist.gov/publication/nistpubs/800_30_r1.pdf. (Accessed 16-6-2013).
31. Nobre, F. F., Trotta, L. T. F., Gomes, L. F. A. M., (1999), "Multi-criteria decision making: an approach to setting priorities in health care", Symposium on statistical bases for public health decision making, Vol. 18, No. 23, pp.3345-3354.
32. Panigrshi S, Kundu A, Sural S, Majumder A K. (2009), "Credit card adds fraud detection: a fusion approach using Dempster-Shafer theory and Bayesian learning". Information Fusion, Vol. 10, No. 4, pp. 354-363.

33. Peltier T. R. (2000), "Facilitated risk analysis process (FRAP)". Auerbach Publication, CRC Press LLC, December 2000.
34. Ramanathan R, Ganesh L. S (1994), "Group preference aggregation methods in AHP: an evaluation and an intrinsic process for deriving members' weights". *European Journal of Operation Research*, Vol. 79, No. 2, pp. 249-265. *International Journal of Computer Science & Information Technology (IJCSIT)* Vol 6, No1, February 2014 44
35. Rot A. (2008), "IT risks assessment: quantitative and qualitative approach". WCECS, 2008, October 22-24, San Francisco, USA.
36. Saaty T. L. (1980), "The Analytical Hierarchy Process: Planning, Priority Setting", *Resource Allocation*. McGraw-Hill, New York, NY, USA.1980.
37. Sadok M, Spagnoletti P. (2011), "A business aware information security risk and analysis method". *Information Technology and Innovation trends in Organization*, pp. 453-460.
38. Schechter E. (2004), "Computer security strength & risk: a quantitative approach". Harvard University, Cambridge, Massachusetts, USA. 2004.
39. Shedden P, Smith W, Ahmad A. (2010), "Information security risk assessment: towards a business practice perspective". In the *Proceeding of the 8th Australian Information Security Management Conference*, pp. 119-130.
40. Shi, H. and Deng, Y. (2012), "A grey model for evaluation of information systems security", *Journal of Computer*, Vol. 7, No. 1 , pp.284-291.
41. Shukla N, Kumar S. A (2012), "Comparative study on information security risk analysis practices". In the *Proceeding on Issues and Challenges in Networking*, 2012, November 2012, pp. 28-33.
42. Sommestad, T., Ekstedt, M. and Johnson, P., A (2010), "Probabilistic relational model for security risk analysis", *Computer & Security*, Vol. 29, No. 6, pp. 659-679.
43. Stolen K, den Braber F, Dimitrakos T. (2002), "Model-based Risk Assessment –The CORAS Approach". 2002. <http://www.nik.no/2002/stolen.pdf>
44. Suh B, Han I. (2003), "The IS risk analysis based on business model". *Information and Management*, Vol. 41, No. 2, pp. 149-158.
45. Syamsuddin, I. and Hwang, J., (2010), "The use AHP in security policy decision making: An open office calc application", *Journal of Software*, Vol. 5, No. 10, pp. 1162-1169.
46. Syamsuddin, I. (2012), "Evaluation of strategic information security with fuzzy AHP method". *American Journal of Intelligence Systems*, Vol. 2, No. 1, pp. 9-13.
47. Tamjidyamcholo A, AI-Dabbagh R. D (2012), « Genetic algorithm approach for risk reduction on information security". *International Journal of Cyber-Security and Digital Forensics*, Vol. 1, No. 1 pp. 59-66.
48. Vorster A, Labuschagne, L. (2005), "A framework for comparing different information security risk analysis methodologies". University of Johannesburg. 2005.

49. Wang C. J., Lin G. Y., (2006), "The model of network security risk assess based on fuzzy algorithm and hierarchy". Journal of Wuhan University, Vol. 52, No. 5, pp. 622-627.
50. Weiss J. D.(1991). "A system security engineering Process". In the Proceeding of the 14th National Conference Security Conference, 1991 Washington, DC.
51. Xiao M, Fan S. X, Wu Z. (2009), "A threat-centric model for information security risk assessment", Journal of Wuhan University of Technology, Vol. 31, No. 18, pp. 43-45.
52. Yang Y, Yao S. Z.(2009), "Risk assessment method of information security based on threat analysis". Computer Engineering and Applications, Vol. 45, No. 3, pp. 94-96.
53. Yazar Z. A (2011), Qualitative risk analysis and management tool – CRAMM, SANS Institute InfoSec Reading Room. 2011.
54. Yuan, C. Li, J., Zhang, R. and Liu, J.,(2013), "Grey and fuzzy evaluation of information system distress recovery capability", 2nd International Conference on Advances in Computer Science and Engineering, CSE2013, pp. 298-302.
55. Zhang X, Huang Z, Wei G., Zhang X.(2010), "Information security risk assessment methodology research: Group decision making and analytic hierarchy process". In the Proceeding of IEEE the 2nd World Congress on Software Engineering, pp.157-60.
56. Zhao D, Liu J, Zhang Z. (2009), "Method of risk evaluation of information security based on neural network". IEEE international Conference on Machine Learning and Cybernetics, Vol. 1, No. 6, pp.1127-1132.
57. Kijo, H. and Luo, J. (2012), " Analysis on the competitiveness of Chinese steel and the south Korean", Software Computing in Information Communication Technology, Vol. 2, No. 1, pp. 451- 460.

**AN APPLIED STUDY ON EDUCATIONAL USE OF FACEBOOK AS A WEB 2.0 TOOL:
THE SAMPLE LESSON OF COMPUTER NETWORKS AND COMMUNICATION**

Murat Kayri¹ and Özlem Çakır²

¹Department of Computer and Instructional Technology, Yuzuncu Yil University, Van, Turkey

² Department of Computer and Instructional Technology, Ankara University, Ankara, Turkey

ABSTRACT

The main aim of the research was to examine educational use of Facebook. The Computer Networks and Communication lesson was taken as the sample and the attitudes of the students included in the study group towards Facebook were measured in a semi-experimental setup. The students on Facebook platform were examined for about three months and they continued their education interactively in that virtual environment. After the-three-month-education period, observations for the students were reported and the attitudes of the students towards Facebook were measured by three different measurement tools. As a result, the attitudes of the students towards educational use of Facebook and their views were heterogeneous. When the average values of the group were examined, it was reported that the attitudes towards educational use of Facebook was above a moderate level. Therefore, it might be suggested that social networks in virtual environments provide continuity in life long learning.

KEYWORDS

Social networks, Facebook, Web 2.0 tools, Education

For More Details : <http://aircse.org/journal/jcsit/0810jcsit05.pdf>

Volume Link : http://aircse.org/journal/jcsit2010_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] Cassidy, J. (2006) "Me Media: How hanging out on the Internet became big business", The New Yorker, Vol. No. 13, pp 50.
- [2] Toprak, A., Yıldırım, A., Aygül, E., Binark, M., Börekçi, S. and Çomu, T. (2009) Social Sharing Network Facebook: I Can Be Seen Then I'm Here, Kalkedon Publishers, Ankara
- [3] Grant, N. (2008) On the Usage of Social Networking Software Technologies in Distance Learning Education. In K. McFerrin et al. (Eds.), Proceedings of Society for Information Technology and Teacher Education International Conference 2008 (3755-3759). Chesapeake, VA: AACE.
- [4] Lockyer, L. and Patterson, J. (2008) Integrating Social Networking Technologies in Education: A Case Study of a Formal Learning Environment. Paper presented at the Advanced Learning Technologies, 2008. ICALT '08. Eighth IEEE International Conference on.
- [5] Boyd, S. (2003). Are you ready for social software? Retrieved 10.01.2010, from http://www.stoweboyd.com/message/2006/10/are_you_ready_f.html.
- [6] Ajjan, H. and Hartshorne, R. (2008) "Investigating faculty decisions to adopt Web 2.0 technologies: Theory and empirical tests", The Internet and Higher Education, Vol. 11, No. 2, pp 71-80.
- [7] Mason, R. (2006) "Learning technologies for adult continuing education", Studies in Continuing Education, Vol. 28, pp 121-133.
- [8] Ozkan, B. and McKenzie, B. (2008) Social Networking Tools for Teacher Education. In K. McFerrin et al. (Eds.), Proceedings of Society for Information Technology and Teacher Education International Conference 2008 (pp. 2772-2776). Chesapeake, VA: AACE.
- [9] Selwyn N (2009) "Faceworking: exploring students' education-related use of Facebook", Learning, Media and Technology, Vol. 34, No. 2, pp 157-174.
- [10] Bartlett-Bragg, A. (2006) Reflections on pedagogy: Reframing practice to foster informal learning with social software. Retrieved 10.01.2010, from <http://www.dream.sdu.dk/uploads/files/Anne%20Bartlett-Bragg.pdf>
- [11] Ferdig, R. E. (2007) "Editorial: Examining social software in teacher education", Journal of Technology and Teacher Education, Vol. 15, No.1, pp 5-10.
- [12] Albion, P. R. (2007) Web 2.0 in Teacher Education: Two Imperatives for Action, University of Southern Queensland, Australia, http://eprints.usq.edu.au/4553/1/Albion_Web_2.0_in_teacher_education.pdf

- [13] Pettenati, M. C. and Ranieri, M. (2006) Informal learning theories and tools to support knowledge management in distributed CoPs. Paper presented at the Innovative Approaches for Learning and Knowledge Sharing, EC-TEL. Workshop Proceeding.
- [14] Boyd, D. M. and Ellison, N. B. (2007) "Social network sites: Definition, history, and scholarship", *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, Vol. 13, No. 1, pp 210-230.
- [15] English, R. and Duncan-Howell, J. (2008) "Facebook© goes to college: Using social networking tools to support students undertaking teaching practicum", *MERLOT Journal of Online Learning and Teaching*, Vol. 4, No. 4, pp 596- 601.
- [16] Genç, Z. (2010) *The Innovation of Web 2.0 in Using Educational Fields: A Facebook Education Application Sample*, Academic Informatics, Mugla University.
- [17] Koçak-Usluel, Y. and Mazman, S. G. (2009), "Social network adoption scale", *Educational Sciences & Practice*, . 15, pp 137-157.
- [18] Mazman, S.G. (2009) *Adoption process of social network and their usage in educational context*. Hacettepe University, Unpublished Master Thesis, Ankara, Turkey.
- [19] McBride, M.C., and S.T. Wahl. (2005) 'To say or not to say?' Teachers' management of privacy boundaries in the classroom", *Texas Speech Communication Journal*, Vol. 30, pp 8-22.
- [20] Fovet, F. (2009) *Impact of the use of Facebook amongst students of high school age with Social, Emotional and Behavioural Difficulties (SEBD)*. 39th ASEE/IEEE Frontiers in Education Conference. Session W2G. San Antonio, TX, October 18 - 21, 2009.
- [21] Hargittai, E. (2007) "Whose space differences among users and non-users of social network sites", *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, Vol. 13, No. 1, pp 14.
- [22] Laghari, K., Yahia, I.G. and Crespi, N. (2009) "Analysis of telecommunication management technologies", *International Journal of Computer Science & Information Technology (IJCSIT)*, Vol. 1, No. 2, pp 1.

RESEARCH REVIEW FOR DIGITAL IMAGE SEGMENTATION TECHNIQUES

Ashraf A. Aly¹ , Safaai Bin Deris² , Nazar Zaki³

^{1,2}Faculty of Computer Science, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, safaai@utm.my ³College of Information Technology, UAE University, UAE

ABSTRACT

Evaluating the previous work is an important part of developing segmentation methods for the image analysis techniques. The aim of this paper is to give a review of digital image segmentation techniques. The problems of digital image segmentation represent great challenges for computer vision. The wide range of the problems of computer vision may make good use of image segmentation. This paper study and evaluate the different methods for segmentation techniques. We discuss the main tendency of each algorithm with their applications, advantages and disadvantages. This study is useful for determining the appropriate use of the image segmentation methods and for improving their accuracy and performance and also for the main objective, which designing new algorithms.

KEYWORDS

Active Contour, Segmentation Enhancement, Topological Alignments, Boundary Detection, image Segmentation, Inversion Technique.

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/jcsit/1011csit09.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/iicsit2011_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Osher and J. Sethian, "Fronts propagating with curvature dependent speed: Algorithms based on Hamilton - jacobi formulations," *Journal of Computational Physics*, pp. 12–49, 1988.
- [2] Bouguet, J. (2000). Pyramidal implementation of the Lucas Kanade feature tracker. Intel Corporation Microprocessor Research Labs: OpenCV Documents.
- [3] Bradski, G. (2000). *The Open CV Library*. Dr. Dobb's Software Tools for the Professional Programmer.
- [4] Coskun, H., Li, Y., and Mackey, M. A. (2007). Ameboid cell motility: A model and inverse problem, with an application to live cell imaging data. *Journal of Theoretical Biology*, 244(2): 169–179.
- [5] Kass, M., Witkin, A., and Terzopoulos, D. (1987). Snakes: Active contour models. *International Journal of Computer Vision*, pages 321–331.
- [6] Li, K., Miller, E., Weiss, L., Campbell, P., and Kanade, T. (2006). Online tracking of migrating and proliferating cells imaged with phase - contrast microscopy. *Proc. Of the 2006 Conf, on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshop (CVPRW'06)*, pages 65–72.
- [7] Mukherjee, D., Ray, N., and Acton, S. (2004). Level set analysis for leukocyte detection and tracking. *IEEE Trans Image Process*, 13(4):562–72.
- [8] Ray, N., Acton, S., and Ley, K. (2002). Tracking leukocytes in vivo with shape and size constrained active contours. *21(10):1222–1235*.
- [9] Smart, J., Hock, K., and Csomor, S. (2005). *Cross-Platform GUI Programming with wxWidgets*. Prentice Hall PTR.
- [10] Zimmer, C., Labruyre, E., Meas-Yedid, V., Guilln, N., and Olivo-Marin, J. (2002). Segmentation and tracking of migrating cells in videomicroscopy with parametric active contours: a tool for cell-based drug testing. *IEEE Trans Med Imaging*, 21(10):1212–21.
- [11] Shtern F. Digital mammography and related technologies: a perspective from the National Cancer Institute. *Radiology* 1992; 183:629-630.
- [12] Feig SA, Yaffe MJ. Current status of digital mammography. *Semin Ultrasound CT MR* 1996; 17:424-443.
- [13] Aylward SR, Hemminger BM, Pisano ED. Mixture modeling for digital mammogram display And analysis. In: Karssemeijer N, Thijssen M, Hendriks J, van Erning A, eds. *Digital mammography* Nijmegen, 1998. Dordrecht, the Netherlands: Kluwer Academic, 1998; 305-312.
- [14] Pisano ED, Zong S, Hemminger BM, et al. Contrast limited adaptive histogram equalization image processing to improve the detection of simulated spiculations in dense mammograms. *J Digit Imaging* 1998; 11:193-200.
- [15] Chan HP, Vyborny CJ, MacMahon H, et al. Digital mammography ROC studies of the effects of pixel size and unsharp - mask filtering on the detection of subtle microcalcifications. *Invest Radiol* 1987; 22:581-589. *International Journal of Computer Science & Information*

- [16] Byng JW, Critten JP, Yaffe MJ. Thickness equalization processing for mammographic images. *Radiology* 1997; 203:564-568.
- [17] Bick U, Giger ML, Schmidt RA, Nishikawa RM, Doi K. Density correction of peripheral breast tissue on digital mammograms. *RadioGraphics* 1996; 16:403-411.
- [18] Nath SK, Bunyak F, Palaniappan K: Robust Tracking of Migrating cells Using Four- Color Level Set Segmentation. *ACIVS 2006*:920-932.
- [19] Koehler A, Schambony A, Wedlich D: Wnt Signaling in Embryonic Development Elsevier 2007 chap. Cell migration under control of Wnt signaling in the vertebrate embryo:159-201.
- [20] Zimmer C, Zhang B, Dufour A, Thebaud A, Berlemont S, Meas-Yedid V, O Marin JC: On the Digital Trail of Mobile Cells. *Signal Processing Magazine* 2006, 23(3):54-62.
- [21] Palaniappan K, Ersoy I, Nath SK: Moving Object Segmentation Using the Flux Tensor for Biological Video Microscopy. *Lect Notes Comput Sci.* 2007, 4810(LNCS):483-493.
- [22] Miura K: Tracking Movement in Cell Biology. *Advances in Biochemical Engineering/ Biotechnology* 2005, 95:267-295.
- [23] Meijering E, Smal I, Danuser G: Tracking in molecular bioimaging. *Signal Processing Magazine, IEEE* 2006, 23(3):46-53.
- [24] Bouguet, J. (2000). Pyramidal implementation of the Lucas Kanade feature tracker. Intel Corporation Microprocessor Research Labs: OpenCV Documents.
- [25] Bradski, G. (2000). The Open CV Library. Dr. Dobb's Software Tools for the Professional Programmer.
- [26] Kass, M., Witkin, A., and Terzopoulos, D. (1987). Snakes: Active contour models. *International Journal of Computer Vision*, pages 321–331.
- [27] Li, K., Miller, E., Weiss, L., Campbell, P., and Kanade, T. (2006). Online tracking of migrating and proliferating cells imaged with phase - contrast microscopy. *Proc. of the 2006 Conf, on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshop (CVPRW'06)*, pages 65–72.
- [28] Mukherjee, D., Ray, N., and Acton, S. (2004). Level set analysis for leukocyte detection and tracking. *IEEE Trans Image Process*, 13(4):562–72.
- [29] Dzyubachyk O, Niessen W, Meijering E: Advanced Level - Set Based Multiple - Cell

Segmentation and Tracking in Time – Lapse Fluorescence Microscopy Images. In IEEE International Symposium on Biomedical Imaging: From Nano to Macro Edited by: Olivo-Marín JC, Bloch I, Laine A. IEEE, Piscataway, NJ; 2008:185-188.

- [30] Li Y, Zheng Y, Doermann D, Jaeger S: Script-Independent Text Line Segmentation in Freestyle Handwritten Documents. IEEE Trans Pattern Anal Mach Intell. 2008, 30(8):1313-1329.
- [31] Ersoy I, Bunyak F, Mackey M, Palaniappan K: Cell Segmentation Using Hessian - Based Detection and Contour Evolution with Directional Derivatives. International Conference on Image Processing 2008:1804-1807.
- [32] Tseng Y, Kole T, Wirtz D: Micromechanical Mapping of Live Cells by Multiple Particle Tracking Microrheology. Biophysical Journal 2002, 83(6):3162-3176.
- [33] Apgar J, Tseng Y, Fedorov E, Herwig M, Almo S, Wirtz D: Multiparticle tracking measurements of heterogeneities in solutions of actin filaments and actin bundles. Biophysical Journal 2000, 79(2):1095-1106.
- [34] Schütz GJ, Schindler H, Schmid T: Single-molecule microscopy on model membranes reveals anomalous diffusion. Biophysical Journal 1997, 73:1073-1080.
- [35] Anderson C, Georgiou G, Morrison I, Stevenson G, Cherry R: Tracking of cell surface receptors by fluorescence digital imaging microscopy using a charge-coupled device camera. Low-density lipoprotein and influenza virus receptor mobility at 4 degrees C. Journal of Cell Science 1992, 101(2):415-425.

**A NOVEL TECHNIQUE FOR IMAGE STEGANOGRAPHY BASED ON
BLOCK-DCT AND HUFFMAN ENCODING**

**A.Nag¹, S. Biswas², D. Sarkar² and P.P. Sarkar², ¹Academy of Technology - Hoogly, India
and ²University of Kalyani, India**

ABSTRACT:

Image steganography is the art of hiding information into a cover image. This paper presents a novel technique for Image steganography based on Block-DCT, where DCT is used to transform original image (cover image) blocks from spatial domain to frequency domain. Firstly a gray level image of size $M \times N$ is divided into no joint 8×8 blocks and a two dimensional Discrete Cosine Transform(2-d DCT) is performed on each of the $P = MN / 64$ blocks. Then Huffman encoding is also performed on the secret messages/images before embedding and each bit of Huffman code of secret message/image is embedded in the frequency domain by altering the least significant bit of each of the DCT coefficients of cover image blocks. The experimental results show that the algorithm has a high capacity and a good invisibility. Moreover PSNR of cover image with stego-image shows the better results in comparison with other existing steganography approaches. Furthermore, satisfactory security is maintained since the secret message/image cannot be extracted without knowing decoding rules and Huffman table.

KEYWORDS:

Steganography, Frequency Domain, DCT, Huffman Coding, Information Hiding.

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/icsit/0203csit8.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/icsit2010_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] DES Encryption Standard (DES), National Bureau of Standard (U.S.). Federal Information Processing Standards Publication 46, National Technical Information Service, Springfield, VA, 1997.
- [2] Daemen, J., and Rijmen, V. "Rijndael: The Advanced Encryption Standard", Dr. Dobb's Journal, March 2001.
- [3] R. Rivest, A. Shamir, and L. Adleman, 1978. A method for obtaining digital signatures and public-key cryptosystems. *Communication of the ACM*: 120-126.
- [4] Pfitzmann, B. 1996. Information hiding terminology," *Proc. First Workshop of Information Hiding Proceedings*, Cambridge, U.K., *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, Vol.1174: 347-350. [5] Wang, H & Wang, S, "Cyber warfare: Steganography vs. Steganalysis", *Communications of the ACM*, 47:10, October 2004
- [6] Jamil, T., "Steganography: The art of hiding information is plain sight", *IEEE Potentials*, 18:01, 1999.
- [7] Moerland, T, "Steganography and Steganalysis", Leiden Institute of Advanced Computing Science, www.liacs.nl/home/tmoerl/privtech.pdf
- [8] N. F. Johnson and S. Katzenbeisser, A survey of steganographic techniques., in S. Katzenbeisser and F. Peticolas (Eds.): *Information Hiding*, pp.43-78. Artech House, Norwood, MA, 2000.
- [9] Li, Zhi., Sui, Ai, Fen., and Yang, Yi, Xian. 2003 "A LSB steganography detection algorithm", *IEEE Proceedings on Personal Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications*: 2780-2783.
- [10] J. Fridrich and M. Goljan, "Digital image steganography using stochastic modulation", *SPIE Symposium on Electronic Imaging*, San Jose, CA, 2003.
- [11] Alkhrais Habes , "4 least Significant Bits Information Hiding Implementation and Analysis" , *ICGST Int. Conf. on Graphics, Vision and Image Processing (GVIP-05)*, Cairo, Egypt, 2005.
- [12] Krenn, R., "Steganography and Steganalysis", <http://www.krenn.nl/univ/cry/steg/article.pdf>
- [13] C.-C. Chang, T.-S. Chen and L.-Z. Chung, "A steganographic method based upon JPEG and quantization table modification", *Information Sciences*, vol. 141, 2002, pp. 123-138.
- [14] R. Chu, X. You, X. Kong and X. Ba, "A DCT-based image steganographic method resisting statistical attacks", *In Proceedings of (ICASSP '04)*, *IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing*, 17-21 May. vol.5, 2004, pp V-953-6.
- [15] H.-W. Tseng and C.-C. Chang, "Steganography using JPEG-compressed images", *The Fourth International Conference on Computer and Information Technology, CIT'04*, 14-16 Sept 2004, pp. 12-17.
- [16] Chen, B. and G.W. Wornell, 2001. Quantization index modulation: A class of provably good methods for digital watermarking and information embedding. *IEEE Trans. Inform. Theor.*, 47: 1423-1443. DOI: 10.1109/18.923725.
- [17] Chan, C.K. and Cheng. L.M. 2003. Hiding data in image by simple LSB substitution. *Pattern Recognition*, 37: 469 – 474. [18] Chang, C.C and Tseng, H.W. 2004. A Steganographic method for

digital images using side match. *Pattern Recognition Letters*, 25: 1431 – 1437.

- [19] SWANSON, M.D., KOBAYASHI, M., and TEWFIK, A.H.: 'Multimedia data embedding and watermarking technologies', *Proc. IEEE*, 1998, 86(6), pp. 1064-1087
- [20] Chen, T.S., Chang C.C., and Hwang, M.S. 1998. A virtual image cryptosystem based upon vector quantization. *IEEE transactions on Image Processing*, 7,10: 1485 – 1488.
- [21] Chung, K.L., Shen, C.H. and Chang, L.C. 2001. A novel SVD- and VQ-based image hiding scheme. *Pattern Recognition Letters*, 22: 1051 – 1058.
- [22] Iwata, M., Miyake, K., and Shiozaki, A. 2004. Digital Steganography Utilizing Features of JPEG Images, *IEICE Transfusion Fundamentals*, E87-A, 4:929 – 936.

**ADAPTIVE FUZZY FILTERING FOR ARTIFACT REDUCTION IN
COMPRESSED IMAGES AND VIDEOS**

P.Ramakrishna Rao¹, Dr.B.Addai², G.Ramakrishna³ and T.Panduranga Vital⁴

**1,3Faculty in Department of Computer Science 2Head of the Department
^{1,2,3}Dr.B.R.Ambedkar University, Srikakulam Etcherla – 532 410, Andhra Pradesh, India.
⁴Associate Professor, Dept.Of Computer Science, Gayathri College of Science and
Management, Munasab Peta, Srikakulam.**

ABSTRACT

In this paper, spatial neighboring pixels are used to deal with blocking and ringing artifacts while temporal neighboring pixels are utilized to remove mosquito and flickering artifacts. To avoid the blurring effect of linear filters, a fuzzy filter is implemented. Fuzzy filter is a specific case of bilateral filters [15], [16]. Fuzzy filters help denoising the artifacts while retaining the sharpness of real edges. In image and video compression, the artifacts such as blocking or ringing artifacts are spatially directional and flickering artifacts are temporally directional. For compressed video sequences, the motion compensated spatiotemporal filter (MCSTF) is applied to intraframe and interframe pixels to deal with both spatial and temporal artifacts. In this work, a novel fuzzy filter is proposed to adapt to the pixel's activity and directions between the pixel of interest and its surrounding pixels.

KEYWORDS

Artifact reduction, flickering metric, fuzzy filter, MCSTF

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/icsit/0211jicsit09.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/icsit2011_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Jerri, *The Gibbs Phenomenon in Fourier Analysis, Splines and Wavelet Approximations*. Dordrecht, The Netherlands: Kluwer, 1998.
- [2] M. Kaneko, Y. Hatori, and A. Koike, "Improvements of transform coding algorithm for motioncompensated interframe prediction errors-DCT/SQ coding," *IEEE J. Sel Areas Commun.*, vol. 5, no. 8, pp. 1068–1078, Aug. 1987.
- [3] X. Fan, W. Gao, Y. Lu, and D. Zhao, "Flicking reduction in all intra frame coding," *Joint Video Team of ISO/IEC MPEG and ITU-TVCEG, JVT-E070*, Oct. 2002.
- [4] S. Sakaida, K. Iguchi, S. Gohshi, and Y. Fujita, "Adaptive quantization control for reducing flicker of AVC/H.264 intra frames," presented at the *Picture Coding Symp.*, Dec. 2004.
- [5] T. Jarske, P. Haavisto, and I. Defee, "Post-filtering methods for reducing blocking effects from coded images," *IEEE Trans. Consum. Electron.*, vol. 40, no. 8, pp. 521–526, Aug. 1994.
- [6] A. Nosratinia, "Embedded post-processing for enhancement of compressed images," in *Proc. IEEE Data Compression Conf.*, 1999, pp. 62–71.
- [7] T. Chen, H. Wu, and B. Qiu, "Adaptive postfiltering of transform coefficients for the reduction of blocking artifacts," *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. Video Technol.*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 594–602, May 2001.
- [8] S. Liu and A. Bovik, "Efficient DCT-domain blind measurement and reduction of blocking artifacts," *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. Video Technol.*, vol. 12, no. 12, pp. 1139–1149, Dec. 2002.
- [9] B. Gunturk, Y. Altunbasak, and R. M. Mersereau, "Multiframe blocking-artifact reduction for transform-coded video," *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. Video Technol.*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 276–282, Apr. 2002.
- [10] S. Oguz, Y. Hu, and T. Nguyen, "Image coding ringing artifact reduction using morphological postfiltering," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Work. Multimedia Signal Processing*, 1998, pp. 628–633.
- [11] H. Kong, Y. Nie, A. Vetro, H. Sun, and K. Barner, "Adaptive Fuzzy Post-Filtering for Highly Compressed Video," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Image Proc.*, 2004, pp. 1802–1806. [12] S. Westen, R. Lagendijk, and J. Biemond, "Adaptive spatial noise shaping for DCT based image compression," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing*, May 1996, vol. 4, pp. 2124–2127.
- [13] S. DelCorso, C. Miro, and J. Jung, "MNR: A novel approach to correct MPEG temporal distortions," *IEEE Trans. Consum. Electron.*, vol. 49, no. 2, pp. 229–236, Feb. 2003.
- [14] A. Leontaris, Y. Tonomura, T. Nakachi, and P. Cosman, "Flicker suppression in JPEG2000

using segmentation-based adjustment of block truncation lengths,” in Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing, Apr. 2007, vol. 1, pp. 1117–1120.

- [15] S. M. Smith and J. M. Brady, “Susan—a new approach to low level image processing,” *Int. J. Comput. Vis.*, vol. 23, pp. 45–78, 1997.
- [16] C. Tomasi and R. Manduchi, “Bilateral filtering for gray and color images,” in Proc. Int. Conf. Comput. Vis., 1998, p. 839846.
- [17] E. D. Gelasca and T. Ebrahimi, “On evaluating metrics for video segmentation algorithms,” presented at the 2nd Int. Workshop on Video Processing and Quality Metrics for Consumer Applications, Jan. 2006.
- [18] B. Zhang and J. P. Allebach, “Adaptive bilateral filter for sharpness enhancement and noise removal,” *IEEE Trans. Image Process.*, vol. 17, no. 5, pp. 664–678, May 2008.
- [19] S. Kim and J. P. Allebach, “Optimal unsharp mask for image sharpening and noise removal,” *J. Electron. Imag.*, vol. 15, p. 0230071, 2005.
- [20] H. Hu and G. de Haan, “Trained bilateral filters and applications to coding artifacts reduction,” in Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Image Processing, 2007, vol. 1, p. 325328.
- [21] Y. Nie and K. Barner, “The fuzzy transformation and its application in image processing,” *IEEE Trans. Image Process.*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 910–927, Apr. 2006.
- [22] K. Barner and R. Hardie, “Spatial-rank order selection filter,” in *Nonlinear Signal Processing*, S. K. Mitra and G. Sicuranza, Eds. New York: Academic, Apr. 2006, vol. 15, pp. 910–927.

E-LEARNING PERSONALIZATION BASED ON DYNAMIC LEARNERS' PREFERENCE

Essaid El Bachari¹, El Hassan Abelwahed² and Mohammed El Adnani³

^{1,2,3} Department of Engineering Science, University Cadi Ayyad

ABSTRACT

Personalized e-learning implementation is recognized one of the most interesting research areas in the distance web-based education. Since the learning style of each learner is different we must to fit elearning to the different needs of learners. This paper discusses teaching strategies matching with learner's personality using the Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI) tools. Based on an innovative approach, a framework for building an adaptive learning management system by considering learner's preference has been developed. The learner's profile is initialized according to the results obtained by the student in the index of learning styles questionnaire and then fine-tuned during the course of the interaction using the Bayesian model. Moreover, an experiment was conducted to evaluate the performance of our approach. The result reveals the system effectiveness for which it appears that the proposed approach may be promising.

KEYWORDS

Adaptive Learning, MBTI, Learning Style, Teaching Strategy, Personalization.

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit/0611csit14.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit2011_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] Abrahamian, E., Weinberg, J., Grady, M. and Stanton, C. M. (2004) "The Effect of Personality-Aware Computer-Human Interfaces on Learning", *Journal of Universal Computer Science*, Vol. 10, No. 1, pp27–37.
- [2] Bayne, R. (1995) "The Myers-Briggs Type Indicator: A critical review and practical guide" Chapman and Hull, .London.
- [3] Bishop-Clark, C. and Wheeler, D. (1994) "The Myers-Briggs Personality Type and its relationship to computer programming", *Journal of Research on Computing in Education*, Vol. 26, pp358-370.
- [4] Brightman, H. J. (2005) "Mentoring Faculty to Improve Teaching and Student Learning Decision Sciences", *Journal of Innovative Education*, Vol.3, pp191-203.
- [5] Brusilovsky, P. (1996) "Methods and Techniques of Adaptive Hypermedia. User Modeling and User-Adapted Interaction", *Kluwer Academic Publisher* , Vol. 6, No. 2-3, pp87-129
- [6] Brusilovsky, P. and Peylo, C. (2003) "Adaptive and Intelligent Web-based Educational Systems" *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Education*, Vol.13, No. 2-4, pp159-172.
- [7] Carmona, C., Castillo, G. and Millán, E. (2008) "Designing a dynamic bayesian network for modeling students' learning styles", *Proceeding ICALT '08, Eighth IEEE International Conference on Advanced Learning Technologies*
- [8] Chaffar, S., Cepeda, G., and Frasson, C. (2007) "Predicting the Learner's Emotional Reaction Towards the Tutor's Intervention", *7th IEEE International Conference, Japan*, pp. 639–641.
- [9] Chaffar, S., and Frasson, C. (2004) 'Inducing Optimal Emotional State for Learning in Intelligent Tutoring Systems' *Lecture notes in computer science*, pp. 45–54.
- [10] Chalfoun, P., Chaffar, S. and Frasson, C. (2006) "Predicting the Emotional Reaction of the Learner with a Machine Learning Technique" *Workshop on Motivational and Affective Issues in International Conference On intelligent Tutoring System(ITS), Jhongli, Tai-wan.*
- [11] Cooper, S.E. and Miller, J. A. (1991) "MBTI learning style-teaching style incongruencies", *Educational & Psychological Measurement*, Vol. 51, No. 3, pp699-706.
- [12] Crosby, M.E. and Stelovsky, J. (1995) "From Multimedia Instruction to Multimedia Evaluation" *Journal of Educational Multimedia and Hypermedia*, Vol. 4, pp147-162.
- [13] DiTiberio, J. K..(1998) 'Uses of type in education' In *MBTI Manual: A guide to the development and use of the Myers-Briggs Type indicator*, eds. I. B. Myers, M. H. McCauley,

and N. Quenk. Palo Alto: Consulting Psychologists Press.

- [14] Ehrman, M. (1990) "Psychological factors and distance education", American Journal of Distance Education, Vol. 4, No. 1, pp10-24.
- [15] El Bachari, E., Abelwahed E.H. and El Adnani, M. (2010) "Design of an Adaptive E-Learning Model Based on Learner's Personality" Ubiquitous Computing and Communication Journal, Vol. 5, No. 3, pp27-36.
- [16] Essalmi, F., Ayed, L.J.B, Jemni, M. Kinshuk, Gaf, S. (2010) "A fully personalization strategy of E-learning scenarios" Computers in Human Behavior, Vol. 26, No. 1, pp581-591.
- [17] Fatahil, S. , Kazemifard1, M. and Ghasem-Aghae1, N. (2009) "Design and Implementation of an E-Learning Model by Considering Learner's Personality and Emotions", Advances in Electrical Engineering and Computational Science, Vol. 39, pp.423-434.
- [18] Felder, R.M., Soloman, B.A. (2003) "Learning styles and strategies" URL Retrieved Marsh 11, 2011 in <http://www.ncsu.edu/felder-public/ILSdir/styles.htm>
- [19] Felder, R.M., Soloman, B.A. (1999) "Index of Learning Style Questionnaire (ILSQ)", URL Retrieved Marsh 11, 2011 in <http://www.engr.ncsu.edu/learningstyles/ilsweb.html>
- [20] Franzoni, A. L., and Assar, S. (2009) "Student Learning Styles Adaptation Method Based on Teaching Strategies and Electronic Media", Educational Technology & Society, Vol. 12, No.4, pp15–29.
- [21] García, P., Amandia, A., Schiaffino, S. and Campo M. (2007) "Evaluating Bayesian networks precision for detecting students learning styles" Computers & Education, Vol. 49, No. 3, pp794- 808 International Journal of Computer Science & Information Technology (IJCSIT), Vol 3, No 3, June 2011 215
- [22] Grant, M. B. & Cambre, M. A. (1990) "Research on teachers' characteristics in relation to a cognitivelearning based interactive videodisc system" Annual Meeting of the American Educational Research Association, April 16-20, Boston, MA.
- [23] Gurka, J., and Citrin, W. (1996) "Testing Effectiveness of Algorithm Animation" In Proc. Sym. Visual Languages, Isle of Capri, Italy, pp360-367.
- [24] Harrington, R. and Loffredo, D. A. (2010) "MBTI personality type and other factors that relate to preference for online versus face-to-face instruction" Internet and Higher Education, Vol. 13, No. 1, pp98-95.
- [25] Hetrick, W. (1993) "Leadership for a time of change", Annual Conference on "Creating the Quality School", March 25-27, Oklahoma City, OK.
- [26] Honey, P., Mumford, A.,(1992) "The Manual of Learning Styles", Maidenhead, Berkshire.

- [27] IEEE- Learning Technology Standards committee. URL accessed on 17 April 2011 <http://ltsc.ieee.org/wg12/>
- [28] Jensen, F.(1996) "An introduction to Bayesian Networks" Springer Verlag
- [29] Judy C.R.T., Chu H.C., Hwang, G.J and Tsai C.C (2008) "Development of an adaptive learning system with two sources of personalisation information", Computer and education: Elsevier, Vol. 51, pp776-786.
- [30] Keefe, J.W. (1979) "Learning styles: An overview", In National association of secondary school, DPP, pp.1-17. [31] Keirse, D. (1998)."Please Understand Me II: Temperament, Character, Intelligence.", Del Mar, CA, Prometheus Nemesis Book Company.
- [32] Klasnja-Milicevic, A., Vesin, B., Ivanovic, M. and Budimac, Z.(2011) "E-Learning Personalization Based on Hybrid Recommendation Strategy and Learning Style Identification", Computers & Education, Vol. 56 No. 3, pp 885-899.
- [33] Keegan, D. (2003) "Pedagogy and support systems in e-learning" Routledge, London, UK.
- [34] Kolb, D.A. (1995) "Learning style inventory: Self-scoring inventory and interpretation booklet", Mcber and Company, Boston.
- [35] Kozma, R. (1991) "Learning with Media" Review of Educational Research Vol. 61 No.2, pp179- 211.
- [36] Lawrence, G. (1984) "A synthesis of learning style research involving the MBTI" Journal of Psychological Type, Vol. 8 No. 1, pp2-15.
- [37] Maldonado, H., Lee, J.R. , Brave, S. , Nass, C. , Nakajima, H. , Yamada, R. , K. Iwamura, and Morishima, Y. (2005) "We Learn Better Together: Enhancing e-Learning with Emotional Characters", Computer Supported Collaborative Learning, Taipei, Taiwan.
- [38] Marin, B.F., Hunger, A. and Werner, S. (2006) "Corroborating Emotion Theory with Role Theory and Agent Technology A Framework for Designing Emotional Agents as Tutoring Entities" Journal of Networks Vol. 1, pp29-40.
- [39] Matta, K. F., and Kern, G.M. (1991) "Interactive videodisk instruction: the influence of personality on learning" International Journal on Man-Machine Studies, Vol.35, pp541-552.
- [40] Montgomery, S. M. (1995) "Adressing diverse learning styles through the use of multimedia"., 25th annual frontiers in education conference, Atlanta, GA.
- [41] Mumford, A. and Honey, P. (1996) "Using your learning styles" Maidenhead: Peter Honey.
[42] Murphy, P. (2002) "Dynamic Bayesian Networks: Representation, Inference and Learning" Ph.D. thesis, Univ. of California, Berkeley.
- [43] Myers, I.B. (1993). "Introduction to Type", Consulting Psychologist Press, Palo Alto.

- [44] Myers I. B., Mccauley, M., Quenk, N. and Hammer, A. (1998) "MBTI Manual : A Guide to Development and Use of the Use of Myers-Briggs Type Indicator" Consulting Psychologist Press, Palo Alto.
- [45] Papanikolaou, K.A., Grigoriadou, M., Kornilakis, H. and Magoulas, G. D. (2003) "Personalizing the interaction in a Web-based educational hypermedia system: the case of INSPIRE" *User Modeling and User-Adapted Int.*, Vol. 13, No. 3, pp213-267.
- [46] Pearl, J. (1988) "Probabilistic Reasoning in Expert Systems: Networks of Plausible Inference" ,Morgan Kaufmann Publishers, Inc. San Francisco,
- [47] Pfeifer, J. (1983) "The effects of personality on success in student teaching", National Field Directors Forum of the Annual Meeting of the Association of Teacher Educators, Jan. 29 - Feb. 2, Orlando, FL.
- [48] Snow, R.E. (1989) "Aptitude-Treatment Interaction as a Framework for Research on Individual Differences in Learning", *Learning and individual differences: advances in theory and research.* 13-60, New York, W.H. Freeman.
- [49] Siadaty, M., and Taghiyareh F., (2007) "PALS2: Pedagogically adaptive learning system based on learning styles", In Seventh IEEE international Conference on Advanced Learning Technologies, Retrieved Marsh 11, 2010 in http://www.cymeon.com/publications/LSP_PALS2.pdf
- [50] Specht, M. and Oppermann R. (1998) "ACE - Adaptive Courseware Environment" *The New Review of Hypermedia and Multimedia*, Vol. 4, No. 1, pp141 -161.
- [51] Tseng, J.C.R., Chu, H.C, Hwang, G.J. and Tsai C.C. (2008) "Development of an adaptive learning system with two sources of personalisation information", *Computer and education*, Elsevier Vol. 51, pp776-786.
- [52] Wolf, C. (2003) "iWeaver: Towards Learning Style-based e-Learning in Computer Science Education", *Australasian Computing Education Conference*, Vol.20, .Adelaide, Australia

PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF WIND TURBINE AS A DISTRIBUTED GENERATION UNIT IN DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM

Ramadoni Syahputra^{1,2}, Imam Robandi¹, and Mochamad Ashari¹

¹Department of Electrical Engineering, Faculty of Industrial Technology Institut Teknologi Sepuluh Nopember, Surabaya, Indonesia

²Department of Electrical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Universitas Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta, Yogyakarta, Indonesia

ABSTRACT

In this paper, the performance analysis of wind turbine as a distributed generation unit is presented. In this study a model of wind power is driven by an induction machine. Wind power that is distributed generation is capable of supplying power to ac power distribution network. Wind power generation system is modeled and simulated using Matlab Simulink software such that it can be suitable for modeling some kind of induction generator configurations. To analyze more deeply the performance of the wind turbine system, both normal and fault conditions scenarios have been applied. Simulation results prove the excellent performance of the wind power unit under normal and fault conditions in the power distribution system.

KEYWORDS

Distributed generation, wind turbine, asynchronous machine, performance analysis, distribution system.

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/icsit/6314jicsit03.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/icsit2014_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] L.L. Lai and T.F. Chan, "Distributed Generation, Induction and Permanent Magnet Generators", John Willey and Sons, West Sussex, 2007.
- [2] R. Syahputra, I. Robandi, and M. Ashari, "Reconfiguration of Distribution Network with DG Using Fuzzy Multi-objective Method", International Conference on Innovation, Management and Technology Research (ICIMTR), May 21-22, 2012, Melacca, Malaysia.
- [3] D. Kusdiana, "Real conditions in Indonesia Energy Needs and Alternative Sources of Renewable Energy", Presented at the Seminar of Renewable Energy, Directorate General of Electricity and Energy Utilization, Department of Energy and Mineral Resources, 3 Dec. 2008, Bogor, Indonesia.
- [4] A. Tapia, G. Tapia, J. X. Ostolaza, and J. R. Saenz, "Modeling and control of a wind turbine driven doubly fed induction generator", IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion, Vol.18, pp. 194-204, 2003.
- [5] R. Syahputra, "Fuzzy Multi-objective Approach for the Improvement of Distribution Network Efficiency by Considering DG", International Journal of Computer Science & Information Technology (IJCSIT) Vol 4, No 2, April 2012.
- [6] Y. Lei, A.Mullane, G.Lightbody, and R.Yacamini, "Modeling of the Wind Turbine With a Doubly Fed Induction Generator for Grid Integration Studies", IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion, Vol. 21(1), pp.257-264, 2006.
- [7] H.Li and Z.Chen, "Overview of generator topologies for wind turbines", IET Proc. Renewable Power Generation, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 123-138, Jun.2008.
- [8] L. Mihet-Popa and F. Blaabrierg, "Wind Turbine Generator Modeling and Simulation Where Rotational Speed is the Controlled Variable", IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications, Vol. 40, No.1, Jan./Feb. 2004.
- [9] S. Kim and E. Kim, "PSCAD/EMTDC-based modeling and analysis of a gearless variable speed wind turbine", IEEE Trans Energy Conversion, Vol. 22, No. 2, pp. 421-430, 2007.
- [10] B.H.Chowary and S. Chellapilla, "Doubly-fed induction generator for variable speed wind power generation" Transactions on Electric Power System Research, Vol.76,pp. 786-800, Jan . 2006.
- [11] M.A. Poller, "Doubly-Fed Induction Machine Models for Stability Assessment of Wind Farms", Power Tech Conference Proceedings of 2003 IEEE Bologna, Vol.3, 6 pp. 23-26 June 2003.
- [12] B.C. Babu and K.B. Mohanty, "Doubly-Fed Induction Generator for Variable Speed Wind Energy Conversion Systems - Modeling & Simulation", International Journal of Computer and Electrical Engineering, Vol. 2, No. 1, pp. 1793-8163, February, 2010.

- [13] S. Müller, M. Deicke, and R. W. De Doncker, "Doubly-fed induction generator system for wind turbines", IEEE Industry Applications Magazine, May/June 2002.
- [14] J.G. Sloopweg, S. W. H. Haan, H. Polinder, and W.L. Kling. "General Model for Representing Variable Speed Wind Turbines in Power System Dynamics Simulations". IEEE Trans. on Power Systems, Vol. 18, No. 1, February, 2003.
- [15] T. T. Chuong, "Voltage Stability Investigation of Grid Connected Wind Farm", World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology, Vol. 42, pp. 532-536, 2008.

FUZZY MULTI-OBJECTIVE APPROACH FOR THE IMPROVEMENT OF DISTRIBUTION NETWORK EFFICIENCY BY CONSIDERING DG

**Ramadoni Syahputra Department of Electrical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering,
Universitas Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta, Yogyakarta, 55183, Indonesia**

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a fuzzy multi-objective approach for achieving the minimum active power loss and the maximum voltage magnitude in order to improve the efficiency of radial distribution networks with distributed generations. Multi-objective function are considered for load balancing among the feeders, minimization of the real power loss, deviation of nodes voltage, and branch current constraint violation, while subject to a radial network structure in which all loads must be energized. Originality of the research is that the fuzzy-based multi-objective optimization in reconfiguration of distribution network including the distributed generation in order to improve the efficiency of the networks. The implementation of the fuzzy multi-objective for distribution reconfiguration on a 70 nodes distribution network with distributed generation is described. The original efficiency of the network is 95.142%. The simulation results show that efficiency of the network is increased to 96.942% by using fuzzy multiobjective method.

KEYWORDS

Fuzzy Logic, Multi-objective, Distribution Networks, Efficiency, Distributed Generations.

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/icsit/0412csit05.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit2012_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] A.M. Borbely and J.F. Kreider, (2001), “Distributed Generation: The Power Paradigm for the New Millennium”, CRC Press, Washington D.C.
- [2] K. Zou, A.P. Agalgaonkar, K.M. Muttaqi, and S. Perera, (2012), Distribution System Planning With Incorporating DG Reactive Capability and System Uncertainties, IEEE Transactions On Sustainable Energy, Vol. 3, No. 1, January 2012, pp. 112-123.
- [3] D. Kusdiana, (2008), “Kondisi Riil Kebutuhan Energi di Indonesia dan Sumber-Sumber Energi Alternatif Terbaru”, Presented at the Seminar of Renewable Energy, Direktorat Jenderal Listrik dan Pemanfaatan Energi Departemen Energi dan Sumber Daya Mineral, Bogor, 3 Dec. 2008.
- [4] S. Civanlar, J. J. Grainger, H. Yin, and S. S. H. Lee, (1988), “Distribution Feeder Reconfiguration for Loss Reduction,” IEEE Trans. Power Del., vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 1217–1223.
- [5] M. E. Baran and F. F. Wu, (1989), “Network Reconfiguration in Distribution Systems for Loss Reduction and Load Balancing,” IEEE Transaction on Power System, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 1401–1407.
- [6] L.F. Ochoa and G.P. Harrison, 2011, Minimizing Energy Losses: Optimal Accommodation and Smart Operation of Renewable Distributed Generation, IEEE Transactions on Power Systems, Vol. 26, No. 1, February 2011, pp. 198-205.
- [7] W.C. Wu and M.S. Tsai, 2011, Application of Enhanced Integer Coded Particle Swarm Optimization for Distribution System Feeder Reconfiguration, IEEE Transactions on Power Systems, Vol. 26, No. 3, August 2011, pp. 1591-1599.
- [8] C. S. Chen and M. Y. Cho, (1993), “Energy Loss Reduction by Critical Switches,” IEEE Trans. Power Delivery, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 1246–1253.
- [9] V. Borozan, D. Rajicic, and R. Ackovski, (1995), “Improved Method for Loss Minimization in Distribution Networks,” IEEE Transaction on Power System, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 1420–1425.
- [10] A. Merlin and H. Back, (1975), “Search for a minimal-loss operating spanning tree configuration in an urban power distribution system,” in Proc. 5th Power System Computation Conf., Cambridge, U.K., 1975, pp. 1–18.
- [11] Q. Zhou, D. Shirmohammadi, and W. H. E. Liu, (1997), “Distribution Feeder Reconfiguration for Service Restoration and Load Balancing,” IEEE Trans. Power Syst., vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 724–729.
- [12] R. Taleski and D. Rajicic, (1997), “Distribution Network Reconfiguration for Energy Loss Reduction,” IEEE Transaction on Power System, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 398–406.

- [13] V. Borozan and N. Rajakovic, (1997), "Application Assessments of Distribution Network Minimum Loss Reconfiguration," IEEE Transaction on Power Delivery, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 1786–1792.
- [14] W. M. Lin and H. C. Chin, (1998), "A New Approach for Distribution Feeder Reconfiguration for Loss Reduction and Service Restoration," IEEE Transaction on Power Delivery, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 870–875.
- [15] Y. J. Jeon, J. C. Kim, J. O. Kim, J. R. Shin, and K. Y. Lee, (2002), "An Efficient Simulated Annealing Algorithm for Network Reconfiguration in Large-Scale Distribution Systems," IEEE Transaction on Power Delivery, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 1070–1078.
- [16] A. Augugliaro, L. Dusonchet, M. Ippolito, and E. R. Sanseverino, (2003), "Minimum Losses Reconfiguration of MV Distribution Networks Through Local Control of Tie-Switches," IEEE Transaction on Power Delivery, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 762–771.
- [17] K. Nara, A. Shiose, M. Kitagawa, and T. Ishihara, (1992), "Implementation Of Genetic Algorithm for Distribution System Loss Minimum Reconfiguration," IEEE Transaction on Power Delivery, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 1044–1051.
- [18] D. Das, (2006), "A Fuzzy Multi-Objective Approach for Network Reconfiguration of Distribution Systems," IEEE Transaction on Power Delivery, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 202–209.
- [19] R.S. Rao, S.V.L. Narasimham, M.R. Raju, and A.S. Rao, (2011), "Optimal Network Reconfiguration of Large-Scale Distribution System Using Harmony Search Algorithm", IEEE Transactions on Power Systems, Vol. 26, No. 3, pp. 1080-1088.
- [20] B. Enacheanu, B. Raison, R. Caire, O. Devaux, W. Bienia, and N. HadjSaid, (2008), "Radial Network Reconfiguration Using Genetic Algorithm Based on the Matroid Theory", IEEE Transactions on Power Systems, Vol. 23, No. 1, pp. 186-195.

**A QUALITATIVE STUDY OF LP-ITS: LINEAR PROGRAMMING
INTELLIGENT TUTORING SYSTEM**

**Samy S. Abu Naser Faculty of Engineering and Information technology, Al-Azhar
University-Gaza, Palestine.**

ABSTRACT

This paper is an attempt to evaluate the Linear Programming Intelligent Tutoring System on the basis of perspective and experiences of instructors and students who used the system in the Faculty of Engineering & Information Technology at Al-Azhar University in Gaza. A phenomenological method, with a focal point group was used. The first objective of this study was to discuss the important aspects of the design and development of LP-ITS. The second was to evaluate LP-ITS on the basis of instructors and students experiences. The third was to explore the perspectives of students and instructors about the implication of LP-ITS skills in lecture hall situations. The results were discussed in terms of the evaluation of the LP-ITS and its implications for learning and teaching activities in the lecture hall.

KEYWORDS

Evaluation of Tutors, Intelligent Tutoring Systems, e-learning systems, AI in Education.

For More Details : <http://aircse.org/journal/jcsit/0212csit16.pdf>

Volume Link : http://aircse.org/journal/ijcsit2012_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] Abu Naser S., Evaluating the Effectiveness of the CPP-Tutor, an Intelligent Tutoring system for Students Learning to Program in C++, 2009, Journal of Applied Sciences Research, Vol. 5(1).
- [2] Crowley R., Legowski E., Medvedeva O., Tseytlin E., Roh E., and Jukic D., 2007. Evaluation of an Intelligent Tutoring System in Pathology: Effects of External Representation on Performance Gains, Metacognition, and Acceptance. J Am Med Inform Assoc. 2007 MarApr; 14(2): 182–190.
- [3] Siddappa, M., Manjunath, A. and Kurian, M., Design, Implementation and Evaluation of Intelligent Tutoring System for Numerical Methods (ITNM). International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Software Engineering, 2009. CiSE 2009, Wuhan.
- [4] Andone I. and Sireteanu N, Heuristic Evaluation of Web-Based Intelligent Tutoring Systems. The 4th International Scientific Conference eLSE, Bucharest, April 17-18, 2008.
- [5] Jeremic, Z., Jovanovic, J., & Gasevic, D. (2009). Evaluating an Intelligent Tutoring System for Design Patterns: the DEPTHS Experience. Educational Technology & Society, 12 (2), 111–130.
- [6] Chien T., Yunus A., Ali W., and Bakar A. (2008). The Effect Of An Intelligent Tutoring System (ITS). International Journal of Instruction On Student Achievement In Algebraic Expression. July 2008, Vol.1, No.2.
- [7] Hategekimana C., Gilbert S., Blessing S., Effectiveness of Using an Intelligent Tutoring System to Train Users on. Off-the-Shelf Software., Proceedings of SITE 2008.
- [8] Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2011). Research methods in education. London: Routledge Falmer.
- [9] Fraenkel, J., Wallen, N. Hyun, H., (2011). How to design and evaluate research in education. 8th edition, Boston: McGraw-Hill Humanities Social.
- [10] Mertens, D., (2009). Research methods in education and Psychology: Integrating diversity with quantitative and qualitative approaches. London: Sage Publications, Inc; 3rd edition, 2009.
- [11] Pring, R. (2004). Philosophy of educational research. London: Continuum, 2nd edition 2004.
- [12] Worthen, B., Sanders, J., & Fitzpatrick, J., (2010). Program evaluation: Alternative approaches and practical guidelines. Prentice Hall; 4th edition, 2010.
- [13] Kvale S. and Brinkman S., 2008. InterViews, 2nd Edition. Thousand Oaks: SAGE. ISBN 9780761925422.

- [14] Patton M., 2001. *Qualitative Research & Evaluation Methods*, 3rd Edition. Thousand Oaks: SAGE. ISBN 9780761919711.
- [15] Lindlof T. and Taylor B., 2010. *Qualitative Communication Research Methods*, 3rd Edition. Thousand Oaks: SAGE. ISBN-10: 9781412974738.
- [16] Creswell, J. (2006), *Qualitative Inquiry and Research Design: Choosing Among Five Traditions*, 2nd edition. Sage, Thousand Oaks, CA.
- [17] Strauss, A. & Corbin, J. (2007), *Basics of Qualitative Research: Techniques and Procedures for Developing Grounded Theory*, 3rd edition, Sage, Thousand Oaks.
- [18] Denzin N., Lincoln Y. (2011). *The SAGE Handbook of Qualitative Research* 4th edition, SAGE.
- [19] Saldana J.,(2011), *Fundamentals of Qualitative Research*, Oxford University Press, 2011.
- [20] Lapan S., Quartaroli M., Riemer F., (2011) *Qualitative Research: An Introduction to Methods and Designs*, Wiley 2011.

M-LEARNING: A NEW PARADIGM OF LEARNING MATHEMATICS IN MALAYSIA

Saipunidzam Mahamad¹ , Mohammad Noor Ibrahim² and Shakirah Mohd Taib³

**Department of Computer and Information Sciences, Universiti Teknologi PETRONAS,
Bandar Seri Iskandar, Perak, MALAYSIA**

ABSTRACT

M-Learning is a new learning paradigm of the new social structure with mobile and wireless technologies. Smart school is one of the four flagship applications for Multimedia Super Corridor (MSC) under Malaysian government initiative to improve education standard in the country. With the advances of mobile devices technologies, mobile learning could help the government in realizing the initiative. This paper discusses the prospect of implementing mobile learning for primary school students. It indicates significant and challenges and analysis of user perceptions on potential mobile applications through a survey done in primary school context. The authors propose the m-Learning for mathematics by allowing the extension of technology in the traditional classroom in term of learning and teaching.

KEYWORDS

Wireless technology, teaching mathematics, flexible learning, m-Learning

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/jcsit/0810ijcsit07.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit2010_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1]. Y. Liang Ting, "Mobile Learning-Current Trend and Future Challenges", Proceedings of the fifth IEEE ICALT'05, 2005.
- [2]. Lembaga Peperiksaan Malaysia. In: Laporan Prestasi UPSR 2008. Kementerian Pendidikan Malaysia, Kuala Lumpur (2008)
- [3]. C. Chee Keong, S. Horani and J. Daniel, "A Study on the Use of ICT in Mathematics Teaching," Malaysian Online Journal of Instructional Technology (MOJIT), vol. 2, No. 3, pp. 43-51, December 2005.
- [4]. C. Joseph Rene and C. Maria Elena Valdes, "Are You Ready for Mobile Learning?", Educase Quarterly, No. 2, 2007.
- [5]. D. Parson, H. Ryu and M. Cranshaw, "A Study of Design Requirements for Mobile Learning Environments", Proceedings of the sixth International Conference on Advance Learning Technologies, 2006.
- [6]. B. Young-Kyun and C. Dong-Uk, "Present and Future Prospects for Mobile Learning in Korea", Proceedings of the 2005 IEEE International Workshop on WMTE, 2005.
- [7]. A. Barker, G. Krull and B. Mallinson, "A Proposed Theoretical Model for M-Learning Adoption in Developing Countries", 4th World Conference of M-Learning, 2005.
- [8]. J. Black and L. Hawkes, "A Prototype Interface for Collaborative Mobile Learning", IWCMC'06, 2006.
- [9]. G. Stead, "Moving Mobile into the Mainstream", 4th World Conference of M- Learning, 2005.
- [10]. M. Keough, "7 Reasons why M-Learning Doesn't Work", 4th World Conference of MLearning, 2005.
- [11]. X. Zhao and T. Okamoto, "A Personalized Mobile Mathematics Tutoring System for Primary Education", Journal of the Research Center for Educational Technology, Vol. 4, No. 1 ,2008.
- [12]. Y. Michal and O. Ben-Zaken, "Mobile Phones in Education: the Case of Mathematics", The Institute for Alternative in Education, University of Haifa, October 2004.
- [13]. Saipunidzam Mahamad, Mohammad Noor Ibrahim, Mohamad Izzriq Ab Malek Foad, and Shakirah Mohd Taib, "Open Source Implementation of M-Learning for Primary School in Malaysia", International Journal of Social Sciences 3:4 2008.
- [14]. Naismith, L., Lonsdale, P., Vavoula, G., & Sharples, M., "Literature Reviews in Mobile Technologies and Learning". Bristol, GB: National Endowment for Science Technology and the Arts. 2004

AN EFFICIENT GAIT RECOGNITION SYSTEM FOR HUMAN IDENTIFICATION USING MODIFIED ICA

M. Pushpa Rani¹ and G.Arumugam²

**¹ Associate Professor in Computer Science, Mother Teresa Women's University,
Kodaikanal, Tamil Nadu, India**

**² Professor & Head, Dept. of Computer Science, Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai,
Tamil Nadu, India**

ABSTRACT

Biometric systems are becoming increasingly important, as they provide more reliable and efficient means of identity verification. Human identification at a distance has recently gained enormous interest among computer vision researchers. Gait recognition aims essentially to address this problem by recognising people based on the way they walk. In this paper, we propose an efficient self-similarity based gait recognition system for human identification using modified Independent Component Analysis (MICA). Initially the background modelling is done from a video sequence. Subsequently, the moving foreground objects in the individual image frames are segmented using the background subtraction algorithm. Then, the morphological skeleton operator is used to track the moving silhouettes of a walking figure. The MICA based on eigenspace transformation is then trained using the sequence of silhouette images. Finally, when a video sequence is fed, the proposed system recognizes the gait features and thereby humans, based on self-similarity measure. The proposed system is evaluated using gait databases and the experimentation on outdoor video sequences demonstrates that the proposed algorithm achieves a pleasing recognition performance.

KEYWORDS

Gait Recognition, Modified Independent Component Analysis (MICA), Human detection and tracking, Skeletonization, Morphological operator.

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/jcsit/0210ijcsit4.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/jcsit2010_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Gavrilu, "The Visual Analysis of Human Movement: A Survey," *Computer Vision and Image Understanding*, Vol. 73, No. 1, pp. 82-98, 1999.
- [2] L. Wang, W.M. Hu, and T.N. Tan, "Recent Developments in Human Motion Analysis", *Pattern Recognition*, Vol. 36, No. 3, pp. 585-601, 2003.
- [3] Jiwen Lu, Erhu Zhang, "Gait recognition for human identification based on ICA and fuzzy SVM through multiple views fusion", *Pattern Recognition Letters*, Vol. 28, pp. 2401–2411, 2007.
- [4] Dacheng Tao, Xuelong Li, Xindong Wu, and Stephen J. Maybank, "General Tensor Discriminant Analysis and Gabor Features for Gait Recognition", *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, Vol. 29, No. 10, pp. 1700-1715, October 2007.
- [5] Liang Wang, Tieniu Tan, Huazhong Ning, and Weiming Hu, "Silhouette Analysis-Based Gait Recognition for Human Identification", *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, Vol. 25, No. 12, December 2003.
- [6] "Gait Database" from <http://www.cbsr.ia.ac.cn/english/IrisDatabases.asp>
- [7] X. Yang, Y. Zhou, T. Zhang, G. Shu, J. Yang, "Gait Recognition Based on Dynamic Region Analysis," *Signal Processing*, Vol. 88, No. 9, pp. 2350–2356, September 2008.
- [8] W.M. Hu, T.N. Tan, L. Wang, S. Maybank, "A survey of visual surveillance of object motion and behaviours", *IEEE Trans. Syst. Man Cybern., Part C*, Vol. 34, No. 3, pp. 334–352, 2004.
- [9] Jianyi Liu, Nanning Zheng, and Lei Xiong, "Silhouette quality quantification for gait sequence analysis and recognition", *Signal Processing*, Vol. 89, No. 7, pp. 1417-1427, July 2009.
- [10] Xiaoli Zhou and Bir Bhanu, "Feature fusion of side face and gait for video-based human identification", *Pattern Recognition, Part Special issue: Feature Generation and Machine Learning for Robust Multimodal Biometrics*, Vol. 41, No. 3, pp. 778-795, March 2008.
- [11] Changhong Chen, Jimin Liang, Heng Zhao, Haihong Hu and Jie Tian, "Frame difference energy image for gait recognition with incomplete silhouettes", *Pattern Recognition Letters*, Vol. 30, No. 11, pp. 977-984, 1 August 2009.
- [12] Seungkyu Lee, Yanxi Liu, Collins, R., "Shape Variation-Based Frieze Pattern for Robust Gait Recognition", *IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, CVPR '07*, pp. 1-8, 17-22 June 2007.
- [13] Chan-Su Lee, Ahmed Elgammal, "Gait Style and Gait Content: Bilinear Models for Gait Recognition Using Gait Re-sampling", *Proceedings. Sixth IEEE International Conference on Automatic Face and Gesture Recognition*, pp. 147-152, May 2004.

- [14] R. T. Collins, R. Bross, and J. Shi, "Silhouette-based Human Identification from Body Shape and Gait," Proc. IEEE Int'l Conf. Automatic Face and Gesture Recognition, Washington DC, pp. 351-356, 2002.
- [15] J. Han and B. Bhanu, "Statistical Feature Fusion for Gait-Based Human Recognition," Proc. IEEE Int'l Conf. Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, Washington, DC, vol. 2, pp. 842-847, 2004.
- [16] A. Kale, A. Sundaresan, A. N. Rajagopalan, N. P. Cuntoor, A. K. Roy-Chowdhury, V. Kruger, and R. Chellappa, "Identification of Humans using Gait," IEEE Trans. Image Processing, vol. 13, no. 9, pp. 1,163-1,173, 2004.
- [17] L. Lee and W. E. L. Grimson, "Gait Analysis for Recognition and Classification," Proc. IEEE Int'l Conf. Automatic Face and Gesture Recognition, pp. 155-162, Washington, DC, 2002.
- [18] Y. Liu, R.T. Collins, and Y. Tsin, "Gait Sequence Analysis using Frieze Patterns," Proc. of Europe Conf. Computer Vision, vol. 2, pp. 657-671, 2002.
- [19] Z. Liu and S. Sarkar, "Simplest Representation yet for Gait Recognition: Averaged Silhouette," Proc. IEEE Int'l Conf. Pattern Recognition, vol. 4, pp. 211-214, 2004. \$!\$ 67
- [20] R. Tanawongsuwan and A. Bobick, "Gait Recognition from Time-normalized Joint-angle Trajectories in the Walking Plane," Proc. IEEE Int'l Conf. Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, vol. 2, pp. 726-731, Kauai HI, 2001.
- [21] A. Bobick and A. Johnson, "Gait Recognition using Static Activity-specific Parameters," Proc. IEEE Int'l Conf. Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, vol. 1, pp. 423-430, Kauai, HI, 2001.
- [22] D. Cunado, M. Nixon, and J. Carter, "Automatic Extraction and Description of Human Gait Models for Recognition Purposes," Computer Vision and Image Understanding, vol. 90, no. 1, pp. 1-41, 2003.
- [23] R. Cutler and L. Davis, "Robust Periodic Motion and Motion Symmetry Detection," Proc. IEEE Int'l Conf. Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, pp. 615-622, Hilton Head, SC, 2000.
- [24] Jiwen Lu, Erhu Zhang, Zhigang Zhang, and Yanxue Xue, "Gait Recognition Using Independent Component Analysis", J. Wang, X. Liao, and Z. Yi (Eds.): Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg, Vol. LNCS 3497, pp. 183-188, 2005.
- [25] B. A. Draper, K. Baek, M. S. Bartlett, and J. R. Beveridge, "Recognizing faces with PCA and ICA," Computer Vision and Image Understanding, Vol. 91, No. 1-2, pp. 115-137, 2003.
- [26] B. Bhanu and J. Han, "Individual Recognition by Kinematic-Based Gait Analysis," Proc. Int'l Conf. Pattern Recognition, 2002.

